

SMAA-QUALIFLEX methodology to handle multi criteria decision making problems based on q-rung fuzzy set with hierarchical structure of criteria using bipolar Choquet integral

Debasmita Banerjee^{a,*}, Bapi Dutta^{b,*}, Debashree Guha^c, Luis Martínez^{d,**}

^aDepartment of Mathematics, Indian Institute of Technology, Patna 800013, India

^bThe Logistics Institute Asia Pacific, National University of Singapore, 21 Heng Mui Keng Terrace, 119613, Singapore

^cSchool of Medical Science and Technology, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur 721302, India

^dUniversity of Jaén, Department of Computer Science, Jaén, Spain

Abstract

The qualitative flexible multiple criteria method (QUALIFLEX) is a convenient outranking technique to handle multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) problems due to its less complexity and high applicability, while the Multiple Criteria Hierarchy Process (MCHP) allows decision makers to deal with the hierarchical structure of criteria set where decision makers can even estimate results for a particular sub-criterion at some intermediate level of the hierarchy. The main focus of our study is the amalgamation of the MCHP and QUALIFLEX methodology with special emphasis to modeling interaction among the criteria using the concept of bipolar Choquet integral. To give the decision makers more freedom for expressing their cognition about membership and non-membership grades, the q-rung orthopair fuzzy (q-ROF) environment is adopted to express the criteria measurement. To facilitate this, it is first proposed a revised closeness index for q-ROF to identify the appropriate ordering. Further, it is aimed to establish a new framework by implementing Stochastic Multi-objective Acceptability Analysis (SMAA) in our proposed extended QUALIFLEX method with the intention of taking into account a variety of parameters compatible with the descriptive information regarding the relative importance and interaction of different criteria provided by the decision makers. Finally, a numerical example based on supplier selection problem is presented to illustrate the proposed methodology in the decision problem.

Keywords: QUALIFLEX, SMAA, q-rung fuzzy set, Hierarchy, Bipolar Choquet integral

1. Introduction

In a real-world situation due to the increasing complexity of the decision-making environment, human judgments are often in-explicit and ambiguous under many conditions and providing precise data may be difficult by the decision makers.^{1,2} Atanassov³ first introduced the theory of intuitionistic fuzzy set (IFS) depicted by a membership degree and a non-membership degree with their summation value restricted by one, to portray

*Both author contributed equally to this manuscript

**Corresponding author

Email addresses: debasmitabanerjee12@gmail.com (Debasmita Banerjee), bapi.iitr@gmail.com (Bapi Dutta), deb1711@gmail.com (Debashree Guha), martin@ujaen.es (Luis Martínez)

the fuzzy character of data more extensively. Further, in the aim of enhancing the capability of IFS to capture and model user-defined membership and non-membership grades, the theory of Pythagorean fuzzy set (PFS) has been developed by characterizing the square sum of the degree of membership and the degree of non-membership less than or equal to one.⁴ Evidently, PFS is more capable than IFS to model imprecision. Recently, Yager⁵ generalized the concept of PFS by allowing the decision maker more freedom to model membership and non-membership degrees and introduced the notion of q-rung orthopair fuzzy set (q-ROFS). In q-ROFS, the sum of the q-th power of the degree of support for membership and the q-th power of the degree of support regarding membership is bounded by one. One can note that, for q-ROFS as q increases, the space of acceptable orthopair membership grade also increases. Therefore, decision-makers would obtain more liberty and refinement with fewer restrictions in providing membership grades. Due to these obvious advantages, several decision making proposal under q-ROFS environment have been put forwarded in recent times .^{6–13}

In practice, where uncertainty present in the environment, QUALIFLEX is a convenient outranking method due to its flexibility with respect to cardinal and ordinal information. QUALIFLEX (i.e., QUALItative FLEXible multiple criteria method) was first developed by Paelinck^{14–16} as a generalization of Jacquet-Lagrezé’s permutation method to solve the multi-criteria decision-making problems with crisp numbers. In the literature, several fuzzy extensions of the QUALIFLEX method have been proposed with application in different domains such as medical decision-making problem,^{17,18} risk evaluation problem,¹⁹ green supplier selection problem^{20–23} or natural resources management problem.^{24–26} Zhang¹⁹ developed Pythagorean fuzzy QUALIFLEX method to address MCDM problems under Pythagorean fuzzy environment. But, PFS can not effectively deal with the elements where the square sum of the degree of membership and non-membership is greater than one. Therefore, to overcome this limitation, the purpose of our study is not only to extend QUALIFLEX method in the q-ROFS environment but also propose a robust decision-making framework for QUALIFLEX by considering the following aspects:

- In complex decision scenarios with a large number of conflicting evaluation criteria, it is quite difficult to obtain compromise among the criteria.²⁷ To effectively deal with these situations, Corrente et al.²⁸ put forward the idea of hierarchical decomposition of the family of criteria, which allows the decision-maker to group the criteria into consistent sub-families from different high-level points of view and thus, assessment of the alternatives or elicitation of preference under a higher-level point of view becomes less cognitive demanding with the reduced number of criteria.^{29,30} Moreover, it assists decision maker by providing a ranking of alternatives not only considering the whole set of criteria but also with respect to any intermediate higher-level point of view. To incorporate this visible advantages of hierarchical decomposition in QUALIFLEX based decision-making model, we adopt the multiple criteria hierarchy process (MCHP) framework.
- In the existing QUALIFLEX based decision making models,^{17,18,21–23} the weighted arithmetic mean has been utilized to obtain comprehensive concordance/discordance evidence against a pair of alternatives rank-

ing order, except the work of Zhang¹⁹ which employ Choquet integral,³¹ to capture the positive (*synergy*) and negative (*redundancy*) interaction among the criteria.³² However, in many real-life scenarios, the importance of a criterion may also depend on the criteria that are opposing to them, i.e., a bad evaluation under a criterion may reduce the importance of the other criteria.^{33–35} Such types of interaction among the criteria, known as *antagonistic effect*, could not be captured within Choquet integral framework.³⁶ To address this challenge, Figuera et al.³⁶ adopted the bi-polar Choquet integral framework,^{37–40} which allow as to model^{34,35} complex interaction comprising of positive, negative and antagonistic effect among the criteria. Therefore it would be reasonable to exploit the concept of hierarchical bipolar Choquet integral³⁵ to compute concordance/discordance measure for a pair of alternatives considering possible criteria interactions in the hierarchical QUALIFLEX model.

- Often, decision maker gives preference relation (\succ) over the alternatives' performance in a form of pairwise comparisons from his/her knowledge and experience. The decision maker's preference over any pair of alternatives (X_{i_1}, X_{i_2}) could be dictated by the binary prefer relation $X_{i_1} \succ X_{i_2}$, which indicates that X_{i_1} is preferred to X_{i_2} . This sort of preference information should include in the QUALIFLEX framework to capture decision maker's indirect preference information.
- Adaptation of the hierarchical bi-polar Choquet integral as a vehicle for the aggregation of concordance/discordance index regarding criteria makes it necessary to obtain certain preferences regarding the interaction of the criteria from the decision-maker which is incomplete and imprecise in nature.^{41–44} In general, there exists more than one set of parameters that are compatible with the preferences provided by the decision maker. As a minor change in the set of parameters may yield a reasonable change in ranking order of the alternatives, the robustness of the results becomes a matter of concern. In this view, we adopt the Stochastic Multicriteria Acceptability Analysis (SMAA) framework that allows us to measure the robustness of the results in terms of several descriptive measures by exploring all the compatible sets of parameters from the parameters space of the preference model.^{45–47}

As evident from the literature presented above, though researchers have made some attempts in addressing the above issues, none of them have been resolved in the framework of QUALIFLEX based decision-making models. This propelled the exploitation of MCHP in QUALIFLEX with the aim of resolving the MULTI-LAYER hierarchical QUALIFLEX model. But this effort also falls short of the target of developing truly realistic representations of MCDM situations as in any real life situation amalgamation of all these aforementioned issues are possible, that remains to be looked into. Thus it becomes clear that the next step of evolution in the framework of QUALIFLEX requires a paradigm that combines all of these issues. These facts motivate us to design a robust decision-making framework for the application of QUALIFLEX in solving the complex decision-making scenarios under q-ROFs environment. Concretely, we propose to apply MCHP to the ranking method QUALIFLEX with hierarchical interacting criteria under q-ROFs environment and encapsulated it within the framework of SMAA

for finding the robust ranking of the alternatives.

To this end, this study is organized as follows. In Section 2, we provide a brief overview of q-ROFS and propose the closeness index-based ordering principle for q-ROFS. A brief primer of bipolar Choquet integral with its' extension for handling hierarchical structure of criteria is provided in Section 3. In Section 4, we propose an extension of Paelinck's QUALIFLEX in hierarchical structure settings under the q -ROFs environment where bi-polar Choquet integral is utilized to compute partial concordance/discordance measure for a pair of alternatives ranking order. Section 5 develops an SMAA based framework to analyze the robustness of the proposed MCHP-QUALIFLEX decision-making algorithm. A practical example is presented in Section 6 to illustrate the working of the proposed approach with the demonstration of the feasibility. Finally concluding remarks are made in Section Section 7.

2. Preliminaries

2.1. Basic concepts of q -ROFS

In this section, we first briefly review basic concepts of q-ROFS and provide some necessary background to develop QUALIFLEX in q-ROFs context using closeness index-based ranking method.

Definition 1. ⁵ Let X be a fixed set. Then an orthopair fuzzy subset A of X is said to be a q-ROFS if it is of the form: $A = \{(x, \langle A^+(x), A^-(x) \rangle_q) | x \in X\}$ where,

1. in q -rung orthopair membership grade $A(x) = \langle A^+(x), A^-(x) \rangle_q$, $A^+(x)$ indicates the support for membership of x in A and $A^-(x)$ indicates the support against membership of x in A .
2. $q \geq 1$.
3. $A^+(x) \in [0, 1]$ and $A^-(x) \in [0, 1]$.
4. $(A^+(x))^q + (A^-(x))^q \leq 1$.

For $q = 1$, q-ROFS reduces to Atanassovs IFSs³ and for $q = 2$, q-ROFS reduces to Yagers Pythagorean fuzzy sets.⁴ Hence, q-ROFS is a further generalized version of orthopair fuzzy set with fewer restrictions in grade of membership. The set of q -rung orthopair membership grade forms a lattice denoted by $L^A = \{\langle A^+(x), A^-(x) \rangle_q | A^+(x), A^-(x) \in [0, 1] \text{ and } (A^+(x))^q \leq 1 - (A^-(x))^q\}$, with the partial order defined by \leq_{L^A} such that, $\langle A^+(x), A^-(x) \rangle_q \leq_{L^A} \langle A^+(y), A^-(y) \rangle_q \Leftrightarrow A^+(x)^q \leq A^+(y)^q \text{ and } A^-(x)^q \geq A^-(y)^q$.

According to Yager,⁵ if $A(x)$ is a q-ROF then the strength of commitment viewed at rung q is defined as $S_q(x) = ((A^+(x))^q + (A^-(x))^q)^{1/q}$. Consequently, the hesitancy associated with a q-ROF is defined as, $Hes_q(x) = (1 - (s_q(x))^q)^{1/q} = (1 - A^+(x)^q - A^-(x)^q)^{1/q}$. Thus one can state that, smaller q indicates the larger the strength of commitment with less the hesitancy or uncertainty.

Figure 1: q-ROF Space

Definition 2. ⁶ Let $A(x)$ is a q-rung orthopair membership grade. Then a score function S of $A(x)$ is defined as $S(A(x)) = (A^+(x)^q - A^-(x)^q)$ where, $S(A(x)) \in [-1, 1]$.

It is obvious that, the larger value of score function indicates the greater q-rung orthopair membership grade.

Definition 3. ⁶ Let $A(x)$ and $A(y)$ are any two q-rung orthopair membership grades with score functions $S(A(x))$ and $S(A(y))$, respectively. Then $S(A(x)) > S(A(y))$ implies $A(x) >_{L^A} A(y)$ or if $S(A(x)) = S(A(y))$, then $A(x) \sim_{L^A} A(y)$.

From the above definition, it is not possible to differentiate between two q-rung orthopair membership grade by comparing score function only. Noticing the drawback of score function, Liu⁶ further developed the accuracy function, which is defined as follows:

Definition 4. ⁶ Suppose, $A(x)$ is a q-rung orthopair membership grade then a accuracy function H of $A(x)$ is defined as, $H(A(x)) = (A^+(x)^q + A^-(x)^q)$ where, $H(A(x)) \in [0, 1]$.

Based on the score and accuracy functions, the partial ordering of q-ROFs can be refined into the total ordering as follows:

Definition 5. ⁶ Let $A(x)$ and $A(y)$ are any two q-ROFSs with the score functions $S(A(x))$ and $S(A(y))$, and the accuracy functions $H(A(x))$, $H(A(y))$, respectively. Then $S(A(x)) > S(A(y))$ implies $A(x) >_{L^A} A(y)$ or if $S(A(x)) = S(A(y))$, then $H(A(x)) > H(A(y))$ implies $A(x) >_{L^A} A(y)$; or if $H(A(x)) = H(A(y))$, then $A(x) \sim_{L^A} A(y)$.

2.2. The bipolar Choquet integral

Here, we first briefly review the concept of bipolar Choquet integral that can effectively model the complex interaction between the criteria including the antagonistic effect. We then provide a concise introduction of MCHP framework and extension of bipolar Choquet integral for hierarchical structured criteria to understand our proposals on bipolar QUALIFLEX and its extension to MCHP framework.

2.2.1. Bipolar Choquet integral for flat structure of criteria

Let $\mathbb{C} = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n\}$ be a set of evaluation criteria. A bi-capacity^{39,40,48} is a function denoted by $\mu : \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{C}) \rightarrow [-1, 1]$, where $\mathcal{P}(\mathbb{C}) = \{(E, F) : E, F \subseteq \mathbb{C} \text{ and } E \cap F = \emptyset\}$ and satisfies the following conditions:

- Boundary condition: $\mu(\emptyset, \emptyset) = 0, \mu(\emptyset, \mathbb{C}) = -1, \mu(\mathbb{C}, \emptyset) = 1$.
- Monotonicity condition: for all $(E, F), (G, H) \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{C})$, if $E \subseteq G$ and $F \supseteq H$ then $\mu(E, F) \leq \mu(G, H)$.

The 2-additive decomposition of the bicapacity μ into two non-negative valued functions as, $\mu(E, F) = \mu^+(E, F) - \mu^-(E, F)$, $\forall (E, F) \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{C})$ where, $\mu^+, \mu^- : \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{C}) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ could expressed as follows:^{37,38}

$$\begin{aligned}\mu^+(E, F) &= \sum_{i \in E} a_i^+ + \sum_{\{i, j\} \subseteq E} a_{ij}^+ + \sum_{i \in E, j \in F} a_{i|j}^+ \\ \mu^-(E, F) &= \sum_{i \in F} a_i^- + \sum_{\{i, j\} \subseteq F} a_{ij}^- + \sum_{i \in E, j \in F} a_{i|j}^-\end{aligned}$$

a_i^+ denotes the degree of importance of criterion c_i when it is in favor of the preference; a_{ij}^+ denotes the degree of importance of the combination of set of criteria $\{c_i, c_j\}$ when they are in favor of the preference; and $a_{i|j}^+$ represents the amount of dependence (antagonistic effect) of the criterion c_i over c_j when c_i is in favor of the preference and c_j is opposing it. Similarly, a_i^- represents the degree of importance of criterion c_i when it is opposed to the preference; a_{ij}^- represents the degree of importance of the combination of set of criteria $\{c_i, c_j\}$ when they are in opposition to the preference; and finally $a_{i|j}^-$ represents the amount of dependence (antagonistic effect) of the criterion c_j over c_i when c_i is in favor of the preference and c_j is against it. Comprehensively, $\mu^+(E, F)$ gives the level of importance of the criteria in E favoring the preference of alternative X_1 over X_2 , when criteria in F are opposing to it. On the other hand, $\mu^-(E, F)$ represents the importance of criteria in F opposing to criteria in E . In addition, the above notations must comply with the following monotonicity and boundary conditions:³⁴

$$\text{Monotonicity} : \begin{cases} a_i^+ + \sum_{j \in E} a_{ij}^+ + \sum_{j \in F} a_{i|j}^+ \geq 0, \forall i \in \mathbb{C}, \forall (E \cup \{i\}, F) \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{C}) \\ a_i^- + \sum_{j \in F} a_{ij}^- + \sum_{j \in E} a_{i|j}^- \geq 0, \forall i \in \mathbb{C}, \forall (E, F \cup \{i\}) \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{C}) \end{cases}$$

$$\text{boundary} : \begin{cases} \sum_{i \in \mathbb{C}} a_i^+ + \sum_{\{i, j\} \subseteq \mathbb{C}} a_{ij}^+ = 1 \\ \sum_{i \in \mathbb{C}} a_i^- + \sum_{\{i, j\} \subseteq \mathbb{C}} a_{ij}^- = 1 \end{cases}$$

With the 2-additive decomposition of the bicapacity μ , the bipolar Choquet of a given vector $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m) \in \mathbb{R}^m$ with respect to bicapacity μ on $\mathcal{P}(\mathbb{C})$ can be defined as:³⁴

$$C_\mu^B(\mathbf{x}) = C_\mu^{B+}(\mathbf{x}) - C_\mu^{B-}(\mathbf{x}) \quad (1)$$

where

$$C_\mu^{B+}(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i \in \mathbb{C}, x_i > 0} a_i^+ x_i + \sum_{i, j \in \mathbb{C}, i \neq j, x_i, x_j > 0} a_{ij}^+ \min\{x_i, x_j\} + \sum_{i, j \in \mathbb{C}, i \neq j, x_i > 0, x_j < 0} a_{ij}^+ \min\{x_i, -x_j\} \quad (2)$$

$$C_\mu^{B-}(\mathbf{x}) = - \sum_{i \in \mathbb{C}, x_i < 0} a_i^- x_i - \sum_{i, j \in \mathbb{C}, i \neq j, x_i, x_j < 0} a_{ij}^- \max\{x_i, x_j\} - \sum_{i, j \in \mathbb{C}, i \neq j, x_i > 0, x_j < 0} a_{ij}^- \max\{-x_i, x_j\} \quad (3)$$

Assuming that \mathbf{x} represents the bipolar preference of the alternative X_ρ over X_β , $C_\mu^{B+}(\mathbf{x})$ provides the concordance evidence that how much X_ρ is comprehensively favor over X_β while $C_\mu^{B-}(\mathbf{x})$ gives the discordance evidence against the preference.

2.2.2. Bipolar Choquet integral for hierarchical structure of criteria

Many real-life complex decision-making scenarios implicitly impose the hierarchy structure of the evaluation criteria that can be handled within the framework of MCHP.²⁸ Such a hierarchy structure of criteria starts with the root criterion at zero levels, which is referred to as a comprehensive objective and then a set of sub-criteria of the root criterion at level one and so on. The criteria at the lowest level of the hierarchy are termed as elementary criteria. The framework of three layers hierarchical structure of criteria set is shown in Figure 2. To describe the MCHP mathematically, we use the following notations:²⁸

Figure 2: Example of the hierarchy of criteria from first level (root) criterion C_{i_1} with $l = 3$

- C_0 indicates the main goal or root criterion and l is the number of level in the hierarchy
- \mathcal{C} is the set of all criteria comprises of elementary sub-criteria set and non-elementary criteria set and $\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{C}}$ is the set of indices of all criteria belong to \mathcal{C} representing position of the criteria located at any level of the hierarchy.
- C_1, C_2, \dots, C_u are the first level criteria

- $C_{\mathbf{r}} \in \mathcal{C}$ with $\mathbf{r} = (i_1, i_2, \dots, i_h) \in \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{C}}$ denotes a sub-criteria of C_{i_1} at the level h and $\{C_{(\mathbf{r},1)}, C_{(\mathbf{r},2)}, \dots, C_{(\mathbf{r},n(\mathbf{r}))}\}$ is the set of sub-criteria of $C_{\mathbf{r}}$ located at the level immediately below, where $n(\mathbf{r})$ denotes the total number of sub-criteria of $C_{\mathbf{r}}$ in the subsequent level.
- $\mathcal{C}_{EL} = \{c_{\mathbf{j}} : \mathbf{j} \in EL\} \subset \mathcal{C}$ is the set of all elementary sub criteria located at the bottom of hierarchy where EL is the index set of all elementary sub-criteria and $EL \subset \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{C}}$ and given by

$$EL = \{\mathbf{j} = (i_1, i_2, \dots, i_l) \in \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{C}}\} \text{ where } \begin{cases} i_1 \in \{1, \dots, u\} \\ i_2 \in \{1, \dots, n(i_1)\} \\ \vdots \\ i_l \in \{1, \dots, n(i_1, i_2, \dots, i_{l-1})\} \end{cases}$$

- $\{C_{\mathbf{r}} : \mathbf{r} \in \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{C}} \setminus EL\}$ is the set of all non-elementary criteria including main criteria set.
- $I_{C_{\mathbf{r}}}$ is the set of indices of elementary sub-criteria descending from some non elementary criterion $C_{\mathbf{r}}$ ($\mathbf{r} \in \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{C}} \setminus EL$) using which an evaluation of criterion $C_{\mathbf{r}}$ can be provided and $I_{C_{\mathbf{r}}} \subset EL$.
- $\mathcal{C}_{\mathbf{r}}^h$ is the set of sub-criteria of $C_{\mathbf{r}}$ located at any level h .

With this description of the hierarchy structure, our interest lies on defining bipolar Choquet integral at any non-elementary node $C_{\mathbf{r}}$. We consider bi-capacity μ on the set $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{C}_{EL}) = \{(E, F) : E, F \subseteq \mathcal{C}_{EL} \text{ and } E \cap F = \phi\}$ as a combinations of all couples of disjoint subsets of elementary criteria. The decomposition measures μ^+ and μ^- are also defined on $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{C}_{EL})$. Form the bicapacity μ , one can define a bicapacity $\mu_{\mathbf{r}}^h$ on $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{C}_{\mathbf{r}}^h) = \{(E, F) : E, F \subseteq \mathcal{C}_{\mathbf{r}}^h \text{ and } E \cap F = \phi\}$ for any elementary criteria $C_{\mathbf{r}}, \mathbf{r} \in \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{C}} \setminus EL$ as follows:³⁵

$$\mu_{\mathbf{r}}^h(E, F) = \frac{\mu(\{c_{\mathbf{j}} : \mathbf{j} \in I_E\}, \{c_{\mathbf{j}} : \mathbf{j} \in I_F\})}{\mu(\{c_{\mathbf{j}} : \mathbf{j} \in I_{C_{\mathbf{r}}}\}, \phi)} \quad (4)$$

where, $\mu(\{c_{\mathbf{j}} : \mathbf{j} \in I_{C_{\mathbf{r}}}\}, \phi) \neq 0$. As earlier, the decomposition of bi-capacity $\mu_{\mathbf{r}}^h$ can be described as, $\mu_{\mathbf{r}}^h(E, F) = \mu_{\mathbf{r}}^{h+}(E, F) - \mu_{\mathbf{r}}^{h-}(E, F)$, $\forall (E, F) \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{C}_{\mathbf{r}}^h)$ where, $\mu^+, \mu^- : \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{C}_{\mathbf{r}}^h) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and defined as,

$$\mu_{\mathbf{r}}^{h+}(E, F) = \frac{\mu^+(\{c_{\mathbf{j}} : \mathbf{j} \in I_E\}, \{c_{\mathbf{j}} : \mathbf{j} \in I_F\})}{\mu^+(\{c_{\mathbf{j}} : \mathbf{j} \in I_{C_{\mathbf{r}}}\}, \phi)} \quad (5)$$

and,

$$\mu_{\mathbf{r}}^{h-}(E, F) = \frac{\mu^-(\{c_{\mathbf{j}} : \mathbf{j} \in I_E\}, \{c_{\mathbf{j}} : \mathbf{j} \in I_F\})}{\mu^-(\{c_{\mathbf{j}} : \mathbf{j} \in I_{C_{\mathbf{r}}}\}, \phi)} \quad (6)$$

Finally, the bipolar Choquet integral of $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{|EL|}$ with respect to $\mu_{\mathbf{r}}^h$ for any non-elementary node $C_{\mathbf{r}}$ can be expressed as follows:³⁵:

$$C_{\mu_{\mathbf{r}}^h}^B(\mathbf{x}) = C_{\mu_{\mathbf{r}}^h}^{B+}(\mathbf{x}) - C_{\mu_{\mathbf{r}}^h}^{B-}(\mathbf{x}). \quad (7)$$

where the positive and negative bipolar Choquet integrals for any non-elementary criteria $C_{\mathbf{r}}, \mathbf{r} \in \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{C}} \setminus EL$ can be

computed as follows:

$$C_{\mu_r^h}^{B+}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{C_{\mu}^{B+}(\mathbf{x}_r)}{\mu^+(\{c_j : \mathbf{j} \in I_{C_r}\}, \phi)}, \quad C_{\mu_r^h}^{B-}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{C_{\mu}^{B-}(\mathbf{x}_r)}{\mu^-(\{c_j : \mathbf{j} \in I_{C_r}\}, \phi)} \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{x}_r \in \mathbb{R}^{|EL|}$ is such that the components corresponding to the indices set $EL \setminus I_{C_r}$ are zeros.

2.3. QUALIFLEX method

In this section, we briefly describe the QUALIFLEX algorithm, which finds the best complete ranking order of the alternatives by exhaustively searching all possible complete preorders of the alternatives on the basis of concordance/discordance measures.¹⁴⁻¹⁶ For this purpose, we consider a $\mathbb{X} = \{X_1, X_2, \dots, X_m\}$ be the set of alternatives whose performance are evaluated with respect to the set of criteria $\{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n\}$. The $U_i(c_j)$ be the evaluation/utility of X_i under the criteria c_j . The best preorder of the alternatives can be obtained by following steps of the QUALIFLEX:^{22,24,26}

Step 1 List the all possible complete preorders of the alternatives by taking permutation of the alternatives $\mathbb{X} = \{X_1, X_2, \dots, X_m\}$ and say \mathcal{P} , where any preorder $P = (\dots, X_\rho, \dots, X_\beta, \dots)$ is such that X_ρ has the better rank than X_β .

Step 2 Define concordance/discordance index for ranking of a pair of alternatives (X_ρ, X_β) in pre-order P under a criterion c_j from the utility as follows:

$$I_j^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) = U_\rho(c_j) - U_\beta(c_j) \quad (9)$$

where $I_j^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) > 0$ indicates concordance and $I_j^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) < 0$ indicates discordance.

Step 3 Find the concordance/discordance for the $(x_\rho, X_\beta) \in P$ under the complete set of criteria as follows:

$$I^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) = \sum_{j=1}^n I_j^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) w_j = \sum_{j=1}^n (U_\rho(c_j) - U_\beta(c_j)) w_j \quad (10)$$

where $w = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)$ is the weight vector of the criteria such that $w_j > 0$ and $\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1$.

Step 4 Compute the comprehensive concordance/discordance of the preorder $P \in \mathcal{P}$ as follows:

$$I^P = \sum_{(X_\rho, X_\beta) \in P} I^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) = \sum_{(X_\rho, X_\beta) \in P} \sum_{j=1}^n I_j^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) w_j = \sum_{(X_\rho, X_\beta) \in P} \sum_{j=1}^n (U_\rho(c_j) - U_\beta(c_j)) w_j \quad (11)$$

Step 5 Find the best complete preorder of the alternatives as follows:

$$P^* = \arg \max_{P \in \mathcal{P}} I^P \quad (12)$$

3. Bipolar QUALIFLEX and its extension to MCHP under q-ROF environment

In this section, we propose the concept of the bipolar QUALIFLEX under q-ROF environment and its extension to MCHP framework to deal with complex decision problems that can be decomposed into hierarchical fashion and analyzed from several higher level view points. The framework of decision making model is illustrated in Fig. 3. At first stage of the framework, we enrich the traditional framework of QUALIFLEX by modelling the complex criteria interaction with the help of bipolar Choquet integral and capturing the uncertainty in evaluation via q-ROF. In second stage, we extend the bipolar QUALIFLEX in MCHP framework. Concretely, We aim to amalgamate the new concepts within the framework of QUALIFLEX by re-defining the key steps of the QUALIFLEX.

Figure 3: Propose framework of Bipolar QUALIFLEX and its MCHP extension

The key steps of the QUALIFLEX is defining concordance/discordance measure to test a ranking of a pair of alternatives under a criterion. To define concordance/discordance measure under q-ROF environment, we first need to define suitable ordering of q-ROFs. In this aim, we propose an ordering method of q-ROFs and describe in the following section.

3.1. Ranking of q-ROFs

It is evident from Section 2.1 that the score and accuracy functions proposed by Liu⁶ did not consider the impact of hesitation present in the information which may cause dissipation of knowledge in the data. To overcome this limitation, Peng et al.⁹ presented a new score function of q-ROFSs based on exponential function with some desirable properties considering all the three components support, oppose and hesitation together. However, to avoid the complication involved in the proposed exponential based score function, here we define a new score function based on the distance measure which quantifies the difference between two q-ROFSs taking into account all three modules. Specifically, we extend the concept of distance measure for Pythagorean Fuzzy Numbers (PFNs) proposed by Zhang and Xu⁴⁹ to q-ROFSs and utilize it to define closeness index of q-ROFS that facilitates the rankings of q-ROFSs.¹⁹ With the same spirit, we can establish the notion of distance measure in q-ROFS domain as follows:

Definition 6. For any two q-rung orthopair membership grades $A(x) = \langle A^+(x), A^-(x) \rangle_q$ and $A(y) = \langle A^+(y), A^-(y) \rangle_q$, the distance measure is defined as:

$$d(A(x), A(y)) = \frac{1}{2}(|A^+(x)^q - A^+(y)^q| + |A^-(x)^q - A^-(y)^q| + |Hes_q(x)^q - Hes_q(y)^q|). \quad (13)$$

Hence from definition 6, it can be easily seen that $0 \leq d(A(x), A(y)) \leq 1$ and $d(A(x), A(y)) = 0$ if and only if $A(x) = A(y)$. Now motivated by the concept of TOPSIS method⁵⁰ which aims at choosing the alternative with the shortest distance from the positive ideal solution and the farthest distance from the negative ideal solution, the distance between a q-rung orthopair membership grade $A(x) = \langle A^+(x), A^-(x) \rangle_q$ and the positive ideal solution $I^+ = \langle 1, 0 \rangle$ is given as follows:

$$d(A(x), I^+) = \frac{1}{2}(|A^+(x)^q - 1| + |A^-(x)^q| + |A^+(x)^q + A^-(x)^q - 1|) = 1 - A^+(x)^q. \quad (14)$$

Similarly, the distance between a q-rung orthopair membership grade $A(x) = \langle A^+(x), A^-(x) \rangle_q$ and the negative ideal solution $I^- = \langle 0, 1 \rangle$ is given by

$$d(A(x), I^-) = \frac{1}{2}(|A^+(x)^q| + |A^-(x)^q - 1| + |A^+(x)^q + A^-(x)^q - 1|) = 1 - A^-(x)^q. \quad (15)$$

Thus, we define a new distance measure to calculate the distances between a q-rung orthopair membership grade and the positive ideal solution (Eq. (14)) as well as the negative ideal solution (Eq. (15)). Based on these, we define the closeness index of the q-ROF as follows:

Definition 7. Let $A(x) = \langle A^+(x), A^-(x) \rangle_q$ is a q-rung orthopair membership grade, $I^+ = \langle 1, 0 \rangle$ be the positive ideal solution and $I^- = \langle 0, 1 \rangle$ be the negative ideal solution, then the closeness index of $A(x)$ is defined as:

$$\mathfrak{C}(A(x)) = \frac{d(A(x), I^-)}{d(A(x), I^-) + d(A(x), I^+)} = \frac{1 - A^-(x)^q}{2 - A^+(x)^q - A^-(x)^q}. \quad (16)$$

It can be easily verified that, for every q-rung orthopair membership grade $A(x) = \langle A^+(x), A^-(x) \rangle_q$, the closeness index $\mathfrak{C}(A(x)) \in [0, 1]$. In the next theorem, we establish the relationship between partial order (\leq_{L^A}) and the closeness index of q-ROFs.

Theorem 1. For any two q-rung orthopair membership grade $A(x) = \langle A^+(x), A^-(x) \rangle_q$ and $A(y) = \langle A^+(y), A^-(y) \rangle_q$, $A(x) \leq_{L^A} A(y)$ implies $\mathfrak{C}(A(x)) \leq \mathfrak{C}(A(y))$.

Proof. Using definition 7, we can obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathfrak{C}(A(x)) - \mathfrak{C}(A(y)) &= \frac{d(A(x), I^-)}{d(A(x), I^-) + d(A(x), I^+)} - \frac{d(A(y), I^-)}{d(A(y), I^-) + d(A(y), I^+)} \\
&= \frac{1 - A^-(x)^q}{2 - A^+(x)^q - A^-(x)^q} - \frac{1 - A^-(y)^q}{2 - A^+(y)^q - A^-(y)^q} \\
&= \frac{(1 - A^-(x)^q)(2 - A^+(y)^q - A^-(y)^q) - (1 - A^-(y)^q)(2 - A^+(x)^q - A^-(x)^q)}{(2 - A^+(x)^q - A^-(x)^q)(2 - A^+(y)^q - A^-(y)^q)} \\
&= \frac{A^+(x)^q - A^+(y)^q + A^-(x)^q - A^-(y)^q + A^+(y)^q A^-(x)^q - A^+(x)^q A^-(y)^q}{(2 - A^+(x)^q - A^-(x)^q)(2 - A^+(y)^q - A^-(y)^q)} \\
&= \frac{(1 - A^+(y)^q)(1 - A^-(x)^q) - (1 - A^+(x)^q)(1 - A^-(y)^q)}{(2 - A^+(x)^q - A^-(x)^q)(2 - A^+(y)^q - A^-(y)^q)}
\end{aligned}$$

Now, as $A(x) \leq_{L^A} A(y) \Leftrightarrow A^+(x)^q \leq A^+(y)^q, A^-(x)^q \geq A^-(y)^q$ thus we obtain,

$$(1 - A^+(y)^q)(1 - A^-(x)^q) \leq (1 - A^+(x)^q)(1 - A^-(y)^q) \text{ and } (2 - A^+(x)^q - A^-(x)^q)(2 - A^+(y)^q - A^-(y)^q) > 0.$$

Which implies, $\mathfrak{C}(A(x)) - \mathfrak{C}(A(y)) \leq 0$. So, $\mathfrak{C}(A(x)) \leq \mathfrak{C}(A(y))$. \square

In order to compare two q-rung orthopair membership grades where the score-accuracy based ranking method fails, one total ordering based on closeness index of q-ROFS can be defined as follows:

Definition 8. Suppose, $A(x)$ and $A(y)$ are any two q-rung orthopair membership grades. $\mathfrak{C}(A(x))$, $\mathfrak{C}(A(y))$ are the closeness indices of x and y respectively, then

- $\mathfrak{C}(A(x)) > \mathfrak{C}(A(y))$ implies $A(x) >_{L^A} A(y)$.
- $\mathfrak{C}(A(x)) < \mathfrak{C}(A(y))$ implies $A(x) <_{L^A} A(y)$.
- $\mathfrak{C}(A(x)) = \mathfrak{C}(A(y))$ implies $A(x) \sim_{L^A} A(y)$.

Example 3.1. For example, suppose $A(x) = \langle \frac{2}{3}, \frac{\sqrt[3]{7}}{3} \rangle$ and $A(y) = \langle \frac{\sqrt[3]{9}}{3}, \frac{2}{3} \rangle$ are two q-ROFNs. Now for $q = 3$, then their value of scoring functions are, $S(A(x)) = \frac{1}{27}$ and $S(A(y)) = \frac{1}{27}$, respectively. Therefore, it is not sufficient to rely on the scoring function to compare two q-ROFNs. But If we calculate their closeness indices, then $\mathfrak{C}(A(x)) = 0.5128$ and $\mathfrak{C}(A(y)) = 0.5135$. Thus we have, $A(x) <_{L^A} A(y)$.

Thus the above Example 3.1 conveys the fact that the proposed closeness index based ranking method for q-ROF has more discriminatory power than the score-accuracy dependent ranking method proposed by Liu.⁶

3.2. Bipolar QUALIFLEX under q-ROFs

Based on the concepts of closeness index of q-ROF and bipolar Choquet integral, introduced in the previous sections, we propose the idea of bi-polar QUALIFLEX under q-ROF environment.

To synchronize with the original form of QUALIFLEX described in section 2.3, we here elaborate a few more decision elements. We reaffirm that $\mathbb{X} = \{X_1, X_2, \dots, X_m\}$ ($m \geq 2$) be the set of alternatives that we intend to evaluate regarding a set of performance measuring elementary criteria \mathcal{C}_{EL} , which are formed hierarchy

structure with intermediate non-elementary criteria (top-level view points). The evaluation of the alternative $X_i (i = 1, 2, \dots, m)$ under the elementary criteria $c_j (\mathbf{j} \in EL)$ is given by a q-ROFS, $A_{ij} = \langle A_{ij}^+, A_{ij}^- \rangle_q$. Note that for the time being our analysis will confine with only elementary criteria set \mathcal{C}_{EL} , i.e. flat structure of the criteria. In fact, there will be no difference between \mathbb{C} and \mathcal{C}_{EL} except the indices notations with the assumption $|\mathbb{C}| = |\mathcal{C}_{EL}|$.

As aforementioned in Section 2.3, QUALIFLEX method evaluates all possible rankings/pre-orders/permutations \mathcal{P} of alternatives' set \mathbb{X} . So, our interest lies into check the compatibility of each possible pre-order $P \in \mathcal{P}$ in terms of concordance/discordance measure based on the evaluation of the alternatives, given via q-ROFs, regarding the elementary criteria under the bipolar framework that allows us to capture complex interaction between criteria.

In the lines of traditional QUALIFLEX method illustrated in Section 2.3, we can say that a pair of alternatives (X_ρ, X_β) from the pre-order $P \in \mathcal{P}$ is in concordance under an elementary criteria $c_j (\mathbf{j} \in EL)$ if decision maker's evaluation for the alternatives X_ρ and X_β under $c_j (\mathbf{j} \in EL)$ provides same order of the alternatives (X_ρ, X_β) as in pre-order P . Otherwise, there is a discordance between the rank of pair of alternatives (X_ρ, X_β) from pre-order \mathcal{P} and decision maker's evaluation. Thus, finding the concordance/discordance for $(X_\rho, X_\beta) \in P$ boils down to rank the performance of the alternatives $(X_\rho$ and $X_\beta)$ under $c_j (\mathbf{j} \in EL)$, which can be facilitated with our proposal of the closeness index based ranking of q-ROFSs in Section 3.1. In this vein, we can define concordance/discordance of a pair of alternatives $(X_\rho, X_\beta) \in P$ for each elementary criteria $c_j (\mathbf{j} \in EL)$ via the bi-polar preference function $I_j^P : \mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{X} \rightarrow [-1, 1]$, which is defined as follows:

$$I_j^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) = \mathfrak{C}(A_{\rho j}) - \mathfrak{C}(A_{\beta j}) = \frac{1 - A_{\rho j}^{-q}}{2 - A_{\rho j}^{+q} - A_{\rho j}^{-q}} - \frac{1 - A_{\beta j}^{-q}}{2 - A_{\beta j}^{+q} - A_{\beta j}^{-q}}. \quad (17)$$

One can observe that a positive value of $I_j^P(X_\rho, X_\beta)$ indicates the concordance of the preference X_ρ over X_β in pre-order P with respect to elementary criteria $c_j (\mathbf{j} \in EL)$, while a negative value represents the discordance evidence of the preference X_ρ over X_β . The neutral value i.e., $I_j^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) = 0$ suggests that there is no evidence to support the preference X_ρ over X_β in pre-order P with respect to the elementary criteria c_j .

Next step is to find the aggregated concordance/discordance evidence for the pair of alternatives $(X_\rho, X_\beta) \in P$ from the pieces of evidence under elementary criteria set. Specifically, we intend to aggregate the bipolar vector $[I_j^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) : \mathbf{j} \in EL]$. In the existing proposal of QUALIFLEX, this aggregation step has been done either by weighted arithmetic mean or by Choquet integral, which is not capable of complex interaction among the criteria, specially, the presence of antagonistic effect between criteria. Therefore, to obtain overall concordance/discordance index for the pair of alternatives $(X_\rho, X_\beta) \in P$ from the bi-polar preference vector $[I_j^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) : \mathbf{j} \in EL]$, we apply the bi-polar Choquet integral, which is capable of capturing such interaction between the criteria. Concretely, by using the 2-additive decomposition of the bi-capacity μ and 2-additive bipolar Choquet integral (Eqs. (1)-(3)), we can compute the overall concordance/discordance index ($I^P(X_\rho, X_\beta)$) for the pair of alternatives $(X_\rho, X_\beta) \in P$

as follows:

$$I^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) = C_\mu^{B+}([I_j^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) : \mathbf{j} \in EL]) - C_\mu^{B-}([I_j^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) : \mathbf{j} \in EL]) \quad (18)$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned} & C_\mu^{B+}([I_j^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) : \mathbf{j} \in EL]) \\ &= \sum_{\mathbf{j} \in EL: I_j^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) > 0} a_{\mathbf{j}}^+ I_j^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) + \sum_{\mathbf{j}, \mathbf{k} \in EL: I_j^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) > 0, I_{\mathbf{k}}^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) > 0} a_{\mathbf{j}\mathbf{k}}^+ \min\{I_j^P(X_\rho, X_\beta), I_{\mathbf{k}}^P(X_\rho, X_\beta)\} \\ &+ \sum_{\mathbf{j}, \mathbf{k} \in EL: I_j^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) > 0, I_{\mathbf{k}}^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) < 0} a_{\mathbf{j}\mathbf{k}}^+ \min\{I_j^P(X_\rho, X_\beta), -I_{\mathbf{k}}^P(X_\rho, X_\beta)\} \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & C_\mu^{B-}([I_j^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) : \mathbf{j} \in EL]) \\ &= - \sum_{\mathbf{j} \in EL: I_j^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) < 0} a_{\mathbf{j}}^- I_j^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) - \sum_{\mathbf{j}, \mathbf{k} \in EL: I_j^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) < 0, I_{\mathbf{k}}^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) < 0} a_{\mathbf{j}\mathbf{k}}^- \min\{I_j^P(X_\rho, X_\beta), I_{\mathbf{k}}^P(X_\rho, X_\beta)\} \\ &- \sum_{\mathbf{j}, \mathbf{k} \in EL: I_j^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) > 0, I_{\mathbf{k}}^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) < 0} a_{\mathbf{j}\mathbf{k}}^- \min\{-I_j^P(X_\rho, X_\beta), I_{\mathbf{k}}^P(X_\rho, X_\beta)\} \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

The magnitude of $C_\mu^{B+}([I_j^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) : \mathbf{j} \in EL])$ represents the evidence of concordance to support the preference order of the pair of alternatives (X_ρ, X_β) in pre-order P while $C_\mu^{B-}([I_j^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) : \mathbf{j} \in EL])$ provides the evidence of the discordance against this preference. Eventually, $I^P(X_\rho, X_\beta)$ provides a gauge of overall concordance/discordance of the pair of alternatives (X_ρ, X_β) in pre-order P .

With the help of $I^P(X_\rho, X_\beta)$, we can obtain the overall concordance/discordance index of the pre-order $P \in \mathcal{P}$ by aggregating overall concordance/discordance index for all possible pairs of the alternatives $(X_\rho, X_\beta) \in P$ with $X_\rho \succ X_\beta$. As we do not provide any preference for any specific pair of alternatives $(X_\rho, X_\beta) \in P$, the simple aggregation rule for finding overall concordance/discordance index of the pre-order $P \in \mathcal{P}$ becomes

$$I^P = \sum_{(X_\rho, X_\beta) \in P} I^P(X_\rho, X_\beta). \quad (21)$$

By comparing the compatibility of the all possible pre-orders from \mathcal{P} via the estimates $I^P(P \in \mathcal{P})$, we obtain the best ranking order of the alternatives P^* as follows: $P^* = \arg \max_{P \in \mathcal{P}} I^P$. For the adaptation of the bi-polar framework, we will refer this extension of the QUALIFLEX as *bi-polar QUALIFLEX under q-ROFS*.

Remark 1. It is important to remark here that when the evaluation of the alternatives under elementary criteria are given by using numerical scale, we could drop the environment information and refer the methodology to as *bi-polar QUALIFLEX*. Note that in this case, our bi-polar preference function $I_j^P : \mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{X} \rightarrow [-1, 1]$, could be defined as follows: $I_j^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) = f(A_{\rho j}) - f(A_{\beta j})$, where $f(A_{\rho j})$ is the utility of the alternative X_ρ under the elementary criteria c_j , derived from its rating $A_{\rho j}$.

Remark 2. The formation of overall concordance/discordance index $I^P(X_\rho, X_\beta)$ by using bi-polar Choquet integral acts as a generalization to capture any form of interaction among the criteria in the QUALIFLEX method. In fact

- when there is no antagonistic effect among the criteria, i.e., $a_{\mathbf{j}|\mathbf{k}}^+ = a_{\mathbf{j}|\mathbf{k}}^- = 0$, the bicapacity reduces to a capacity and computation of $I^P(X_\rho, X_\beta)$ becomes Choquet integral;
- when there is no interaction among the criteria, i.e., $a_{\mathbf{j}\mathbf{k}}^+ = a_{\mathbf{ij}}^- = a_{\mathbf{j}|\mathbf{k}}^+ = a_{\mathbf{j}|\mathbf{k}}^- = 0$, the computation of $I^P(X_\rho, X_\beta)$ becomes weighted average aggregation.

Thus, our bi-polar framework generalizes the existing approaches of QUALIFLEX methodology without not accounting information format to evaluate the alternatives against the elementary criteria.

3.3. MCHP extension of bi-polar QUALIFLEX under q-ROFS

So far, we have considered the flat structure of the elementary criteria. With the proposal of bi-polar QUALIFLEX and the concept of hierarchical bi-polar Choquet integral in this section, we will extend the bi-polar QUALIFLEX under q-ROFS to the scenario, where criteria are assembled in a hierarchy.

As hierarchy structure allows us to analyze the decision from the high-level points of view, we are interested to find the results by bipolar QUALIFLEX at the intermediate node of the hierarchy. In this light, the overall concordance and discordance for a pair of alternatives $(X_\rho, X_\beta) \in P$ with respect to the non-elementary node $C_{\mathbf{r}}$ in the hierarchy can be defined with the help of hierarchical bipolar Choquet integral (Eqs. (7) and (8)) and the proposal of $I^P(X_\rho, X_\beta)$ (Eqs. (18)-(20)) as follows:

Definition 9. Let $P \in \mathcal{P}$ be a pre-order or ranking of the alternatives \mathbb{X} . For any pair of alternatives $(X_\rho, X_\beta) \in P$ such that X_ρ ranks higher than X_β and non-elementary node $C_{\mathbf{r}}$, we define:

- the overall concordance evidence for $X_\rho \succ X_\beta$ at $C_{\mathbf{r}}$:

$$I_{\mathbf{r}}^{P+}(X_\rho, X_\beta) = C_{\mu_{\mathbf{r}}^h}^{B+}([I_{\mathbf{j}}^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) : \mathbf{j} \in EL]_{\mathbf{r}}) = \frac{C_{\mu}^{B+}([I_{\mathbf{j}}^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) : \mathbf{j} \in EL]_{\mathbf{r}})}{\mu^+(\{c_{\mathbf{j}} : \mathbf{j} \in I_{C_{\mathbf{r}}}\}, \emptyset)} \quad (22)$$

- the overall discordance evidence for $X_\rho \succ X_\beta$ at $C_{\mathbf{r}}$:

$$I_{\mathbf{r}}^{P-}(X_\rho, X_\beta) = C_{\mu_{\mathbf{r}}^h}^{B-}([I_{\mathbf{j}}^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) : \mathbf{j} \in EL]_{\mathbf{r}}) = \frac{C_{\mu}^{B-}([I_{\mathbf{j}}^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) : \mathbf{j} \in EL]_{\mathbf{r}})}{\mu^-(\{\emptyset, c_{\mathbf{j}} : \mathbf{j} \in I_{C_{\mathbf{r}}}\})} \quad (23)$$

- the overall concordance/discordance evidence for $X_\rho \succ X_\beta$ at $C_{\mathbf{r}}$:

$$I_{\mathbf{r}}^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) = C_{\mu_{\mathbf{r}}^h}^B([I_{\mathbf{j}}^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) : \mathbf{j} \in EL]_{\mathbf{r}}) = \frac{C_{\mu}^B([I_{\mathbf{j}}^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) : \mathbf{j} \in EL]_{\mathbf{r}})}{\mu(\{c_{\mathbf{j}} : \mathbf{j} \in I_{C_{\mathbf{r}}}, \emptyset\})} \quad (24)$$

where the bi-polar preference vector $[I_{\mathbf{j}}^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) : \mathbf{j} \in EL]_{\mathbf{r}}$ is an extension of the vector from $[-1, 1]^{|I_{C_{\mathbf{r}}}|}$ to $[-1, 1]^{|EL|}$ and defined as follows:

$$[I_{\mathbf{j}}^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) : \mathbf{j} \in EL]_{\mathbf{r}} = \begin{cases} I_{\mathbf{j}}^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) & \text{if } \mathbf{j} \in I_{C_{\mathbf{r}}} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (25)$$

On the basis of Definition 9, we shall define the overall concordance/discordance index of a pre-order $P \in \mathcal{P}$ as follows:

Definition 10. For any pre-order $P \in \mathcal{P}$, the overall concordance/discordance evidence at non-elementary node $C_{\mathbf{r}}$ is given by

$$I_{\mathbf{r}}^P = \sum_{(X_\rho, X_\beta) \in P} I_{\mathbf{r}}^P(X_\rho, X_\beta) \quad (26)$$

Finally, the most suitable pre-order $P_{\mathbf{r}}^*$ of the alternatives at the node $C_{\mathbf{r}}$ could be find as follows:

$$P_{\mathbf{r}}^* = \arg \max_{P \in \mathcal{P}} I_{\mathbf{r}}^P \quad (27)$$

By using of Eqs. (22)-(27), we can find the best possible ranking order of the alternatives at any non-elementary node $C_{\mathbf{r}}$ in the hierarchy. Thus, one would be able to analyze the decision from the different top-level point of views. Note that when we attempt to derive the decision at the root node C_0 , the bipolar QUALIFLEX under q-ROFs, introduced earlier, is restored. Indeed, the proposed hierarchical bipolar QUALIFLEX under q-ROFSs is not only a generalization of our proposal of bipolar QUALIFLEX under q-ROFS but also generalizes the classical QUALIFLEX by considering hierarchical structure of criteria and complex interaction between criteria with antagonistic effect. However, the complexity of the proposed generalized decision model increases dramatically in terms of the requirement of the number of model parameters.

4. Robustness analysis through SMAA

In this section, we overlay the indirect elicitation framework for the model parameters through the incomplete preference information from the decision maker and analyze the robustness of the decision outcome by adopting SMAA framework.

4.1. Indirect elicitation of preferences for identifying bicapacity

Adaptation of the bipolar Choquet integral as a vehicle for aggregation in our proposal increases the complexity of the decision model even though we have considered the simplest 2-additive form of bipolar Choquet integral. In fact, to apply the 2-additive bipolar Choquet integral in hierarchical structure, the decision maker requires to provide, $\eta = |C_{EL}| + \binom{|C_{EL}|}{2} + 2 \cdot \binom{|C_{EL}|}{2}$ parameters associated with the 2-additive bicapacity, which is not only

cognitively high demanding even for the moderate number of elementary criteria but also impossible to ascertain the parameters precisely.

To address this, here we embrace the framework of indirect preference elicitation method, which seeks to elicit the parameters by asking the decision maker to provide some indirect preference information on the importance between criteria, the interaction between criteria and antagonistic effect between criteria.⁵¹ Finally, the parameters that are compatible with the decision maker's indirect preference information are inferred. Further, decision maker feels more comfortable to express such preference information in terms of incomplete knowledge, which could be modeled effectively via linear inequalities.⁵² We take into account the decision maker's preference for both elementary and non-elementary criteria in the hierarchy and explain its translation into linear inequalities as follows:

- decision maker's preference for the importance of the elementary and non-elementary criteria:
 - a crude approximation about the importance of the elementary criterion c_j can be translated into the linear inequality $lb_j \leq a_j \leq ub_j$
 - elementary criterion c_{j_1} is more important than c_{j_2} can be translated into linear inequality $a_{j_1} > a_{j_2}$
 - elementary criterion c_{j_1} and c_{j_2} are equally important can be translated into linear equality $a_{j_1} = a_{j_2}$
 - non-elementary criteria C_{r_1} is more important than C_{r_1} can be translated into linear inequality

$$\sum_{j \in I_{C_{r_1}}} a_j > \sum_{j \in I_{C_{r_2}}} a_j$$

- decision maker's preference for the interaction between elementary and non-elementary criteria:
 - elementary criteria c_{j_1} and c_{j_2} are positively interacting can be translated into linear inequality $a_{j_1 j_2} > 0$
 - elementary criteria c_{j_1} and c_{j_2} are negatively interacting can be translated into linear inequality $a_{j_1 j_2} < 0$
 - the antagonistic effect that the elementary criteria c_{j_1} exercise over c_{j_2} can be translated into linear inequality $a_{j_1 | j_2}^+ < 0$
 - non-elementary criteria C_{r_1} and C_{r_2} are positively interacting can be translated into linear inequality $\sum_{j_1 \in I_{C_{r_1}} j_2 \in I_{C_{r_2}}} a_{j_1 j_2} > 0$
 - non-elementary criteria C_{r_1} and C_{r_2} are negatively interacting can be translated into linear inequality $\sum_{j_1 \in I_{C_{r_1}} j_2 \in I_{C_{r_2}}} a_{j_1 j_2} < 0$
 - the antagonistic effect that the elementary criteria C_{r_1} exercise over C_{r_2} can be translated into linear inequality $\sum_{j_1 \in I_{C_{r_1}} j_2 \in I_{C_{r_2}}} a_{j_1 | j_2} < 0$
- decision maker's preference on the alternatives at non-elementary and root node

- X_{i_1} is preferred to X_{i_2} at the non-elementary criteria node C_r can be translated into $I_r(X_{i_1}, X_{i_2}) > 0$.
- X_{i_1} is preferred to X_{i_2} at the root node node C_0 can be translated into $I_0(X_{i_1}, X_{i_2}) > 0$

It is important to note here that we have considered the symmetric bipolar Choquet integral to restrict the concordance evidence for the pair of alternatives from pre-order P is same as the discordance evidence against that pair of alternatives. This fact imposes the following condition on the bicapacity:³⁴ $a_j^+ = a_j^- = a_j$; $a_{j_1 j_2}^+ = a_{j_1 j_2}^- = a_{j_1 j_2}$; $a_{j|j_1}^+ = a_{j|j_1}^-$ for $\mathbf{j}, \mathbf{j}_1, \mathbf{j}_2 \in EL$. These notations are reflected in the above mentioned preference elicitation process. The decision maker's preference for the parameters of bicapacity with the following monotonicity and boundary conditions:

$$\begin{cases} a_j + \sum_{j_1 \in E} a_{j j_1} + \sum_{j_1 \in F} a_{j|j_1}^+ \geq 0, \forall \mathbf{j} \in EL, \forall (E \cup \{\mathbf{j}\}, F) \in P(\mathcal{C}_{EL}) \\ a_j + \sum_{j_1 \in F} a_{j j_1} + \sum_{j_1 \in E} a_{j|j_1}^+ \geq 0, \forall \mathbf{j} \in EL, \forall (E, F \cup \{\mathbf{j}\}) \in P(\mathcal{C}_{EL}) \\ \sum_{j \in EL} a_j + \sum_{\{\mathbf{j}, \mathbf{j}_1\} \subseteq EL} a_{j, j_1} = 1 \end{cases}$$

form the parameters space for the hierarchical bipolar QUALIFLEX decision model under q-ROFS environment. Now our aim is to check the consistency of the given preference information and find the parameters of the bicapacity that are compatible with the given preference information. For this purpose, we are going to adopt the linear programming framework.

Let ε^{DM} be the combined set of all constraints related to decision maker's preference information including the boundary and monotonicity constrains of 2-additive capacities. Note that the strict inequalities presence in the preference information will be converted to weak inequalities by adding ϵ in ε^{DM} . For checking the consistency and finding at least one set of parameters for bicapacity that are compatible with preference, we attempt to solve the following linear programming problem:

$$\begin{cases} \epsilon^* = \max \epsilon \\ \text{subject to, } \varepsilon^{DM} \end{cases} \quad (28)$$

If ε^{DM} is feasible and $\epsilon^* > 0$, then the preference, provided by the decision maker, is consistent and there exist at least one set of parameters associated with the bicapacity that are compatible with the given preference. When ε^{DM} is infeasible or $\epsilon^* \leq 0$, then there exists inconsistency in the preference given by the decision maker and that can be resolved by finding the minimum set of constrains resulting in-feasibility with the proposal of Mousseau et al.⁵³

It is needless to say that the existence of a compatible set of parameters guarantee that there exist infinitely many such sets of parameters that are compatible with the given preference. In such a scenario, making a decision based on a single set of compatible parameters not only unable to reflect exact uncertain scenario but also pose a concern of reliability and robustness of the decision outcome. This fact stems the idea of adopting the SMAA

framework to consider all the compatible set of parameters in the decision-making process and reflect its impact on the final decision outcomes.

4.2. SMAA framework for MCHP-bipolar QUALIFLEX under q-ROFS

The SMAA methodology is a decision aiding tool for the discrete decision-making problems, where assessments of alternatives regarding the criteria and some preference model parameters are not precisely known.⁵⁴ Due to its capability of capturing a wide variety of uncertainty and to address the robustness concerns of the decision outcomes, SMAA framework has been coupled with a variety of the decision-making models.⁵⁵ Specifically, SMAA method analyzes the uncertainty and robustness perspectives of the preference model by exploring the space of the parameters that are compatible with the decision maker's given preference and the space of evaluation where the alternatives' are evaluated against the set of criteria. In our case, we are going to assume that there is no variation in the evaluation of the alternatives and so, our main concern will be sampling compatible set of parameters from the space ε^{DM} . As the parameters space, ε^{DM} is bounded by a set of linear inequalities, we can apply the Hit-And-Run algorithm to sample the space ε^{DM} .

In fact, our SMAA framework for MCHP-bipolar QUALIFLEX under q-ROFS works in an iterative manner, where we perform the Hit-and-Run algorithm to generate the required number of samples of a compatible set of parameters. Afterwards, for each of sampled compatible set of parameters, we employ the MCHP-bipolar QUALIFLEX under q-ROFS method and find the best possible pre-order for the alternatives at different nodes (non-elementary criteria nodes) of the hierarchy. From each of the identified best pre-order of the alternatives, we can track down the ranking position of each alternative and the pairwise preference of the alternatives and subsequently, we can compute the following descriptive measures associated with SMAA that exhibit the robustness:

- *rank acceptability index (RAI) at non-elementary node $C_{\mathbf{r}}$ ($b_{\mathbf{r}}^k(X_i)$):* it provides us the frequencies at which the alternative X_i occupies the k -th ranking position for all sampled compatible set of parameters at the non-elementary node $C_{\mathbf{r}}$. The index $b_{\mathbf{r}}^1(X_i)$ represents the frequency of obtaining the first ranking positions by the alternative X_i .
- *pairwise winning index (PWI) at non-elementary node $C_{\mathbf{r}}$ ($p_{\mathbf{r}}(X_{i_1}, X_{i_2})$):* it provides us the frequencies at which the alternative X_{i_1} preferred over X_{i_2} for all sampled compatible set of parameters at the non-elementary node $C_{\mathbf{r}}$.

To ease of understanding the SMAA framework for MCHP-bipolar QUALIFLEX under q-ROFS and computational aspects, we describe our decision-making algorithm in a step-wise fashion as follows:

Step 1 Find the hierarchical structure of the criteria by MCHP, identifying the subsets of elementary criteria ($c_j(j \in EL)$) and non-elementary criteria ($C_{\mathbf{r}}(\mathbf{r} \in I_{C_{\mathbf{r}}} \setminus EL)$), up to the root criterion.

Step 2 Decision maker's assessments of the alternatives $\mathbb{X} = \{X_1, X_2, \dots, X_m\}$ against the elementary criteria ($c_j(\mathbf{j} \in EL)$) are represented by the q-ROFS $A_{ij} = \langle A_{sj}^+, A_{ij}^- \rangle_q$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, m, \mathbf{j} \in EL$).

Step 3 Decision maker is asked to provide the preference information through comparisons between criteria, interaction between criteria and antagonistic effect between criteria at different levels of the hierarchy.

Step 4 Based on the decision maker's preference, the optimization model (28) is formed and solved to check the existence of a compatible set of parameters.

Step 5 Generate the all possible pre-orders \mathcal{P} of the alternatives \mathbb{X} via permutation.

Step 6 Set the maximum number of iteration to K . By using Hit-And-Run algorithm finds K samples of the compatible set of parameters from ε^{DM} and for each sample execute Step 7.

Step 7 For each \mathbf{k} -th iteration:

7.1 for each non-elementary criteria $C_{\mathbf{r}}(\mathbf{r} \in I_C \setminus EL)$

7.1.1 for each $P \in \mathcal{P}$

- for each $(X_\rho, X_\beta) \in P$ find concordance/discordance indices $I_{\mathbf{j}}^P(X_\rho, X_\beta)(\mathbf{j} \in I_{C_{\mathbf{r}}})$ by using Eq. (17)
- for each $(X_\rho, X_\beta) \in P$ find overall concordance/discordance evidence $I_{\mathbf{r}}^P(X_\rho, X_\beta)$ by Eq. (24)
- find overall concordance/discordance evidence for the pre-order $P \in \mathcal{P}$, $I_{\mathbf{r}}^P$ by Eq. (26).

7.1.2 find the best pre-order $P_{\mathbf{r}}^*$ by Eq. (27)

7.2 Goto to step 7.1 if all non-elementary nodes are not covered

Step 8 If $\mathbf{k} < K$ the return to step 7.

Step 9 for each non-elementary criteria $C_{\mathbf{r}}(\mathbf{r} \in I_C \setminus EL)$

- compute the rank acceptability indices $b_{\mathbf{r}}^k(X_i)$ by the ratio of total no of times X_i occupy the k -th ranking position over total number of iterations K for all $i, k = 1, 2, \dots, m$
- compute pairwise winning indices $p_{\mathbf{r}}(X_{i_1}, X_{i_2})$ by the ratio of total number of times X_{i_1} obtains better ranking position than X_{i_2} over total number of iterations K .

Step 10 Goto step 9 as long as all the non-elementary nodes are covered

Figure 4: Flow chart of the proposed methodology

5. Numerical example

In this section, we provide a didactic example to illustrate the application of the proposed SMAA framework for bipolar QUALIFLEX under q-ROFS in the real-life decision problem.

Let us consider the supplier selection problem for an automotive company. The main aim of the company is to purchase the products from those suppliers who can provide that not only at the lowest costs with the best quality but also in a socially and environmentally responsible manner. With these perspectives of the company, the four potential suppliers are evaluated from the following three aspects: Management and organization (M&O), External perception (EP), Environmental issue (EVS). Further, these three high level points of view are measured by a

set of elementary criteria: Strategy and Organization (S&O), Internal Management (IM), Supplier Management (SM), Reputation and Market Structure (R&MS), Certification (CT), Environmental Management (EM) and Waste Disposal (WD). We construct the hierarchy structure of the supplier evaluation by placing the three key aspects at the intermediate level of hierarchy and elementary criteria at the bottom of the hierarchy. The hierarchy of the criteria is depicted in Fig. 5. In accordance to hierarchy structure description, here $\{C_0, C_1, C_2, C_3\}$ is the set of non-elementary criteria with root node C_0 , $C_{EL} = \{c_{(1,1)}, c_{(1,2)}, c_{(1,2)}, c_{(2,1)}, c_{(2,2)}, c_{(3,1)}, c_{(3,2)}\}$ is the set of elementary criteria, $EL = \{(1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 2), (2, 1), (2, 2), (3, 1), (3, 2)\}$ is the indices of the elementary criteria, $I_{C_1} = \{(1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3)\}$ is the indices of the elementary criteria descending from the non-elementary criteria C_1 and similarly, $I_{C_2} = \{(2, 1), (2, 2)\}$ and $I_{C_3} = \{(3, 1), (3, 2)\}$.

We denote the potential set of suppliers as $\mathbb{X} = \{X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4\}$. Decision maker evaluates the potential suppliers against the elementary criteria $c_j, j \in EL$ by using q-ROFS and that are summarized in Table I.

Figure 5: Hierarchy structure of the criteria for supplier selection

Table I: q-rung orthopair fuzzy decision matrix

...	$c_{(1,1)}$	$c_{(1,2)}$	$c_{(1,3)}$	$c_{(2,1)}$	$c_{(2,2)}$	$c_{(3,1)}$	$c_{(3,2)}$
X_1	$\langle 0.8, 0.2 \rangle$	$\langle 0.5, 0.4 \rangle$	$\langle 0.7, 0.2 \rangle$	$\langle 0.7, 0.4 \rangle$	$\langle 0.65, 0.3 \rangle$	$\langle 0.8, 0.2 \rangle$	$\langle 0.6, 0.1 \rangle$
X_2	$\langle 0.7, 0.1 \rangle$	$\langle 0.5, 0.3 \rangle$	$\langle 0.7, 0.3 \rangle$	$\langle 0.9, 0.25 \rangle$	$\langle 0.8, 0.4 \rangle$	$\langle 0.9, 0.45 \rangle$	$\langle 0.3, 0.5 \rangle$
X_3	$\langle 0.6, 0.2 \rangle$	$\langle 0.6, 0.2 \rangle$	$\langle 0.8, 0.1 \rangle$	$\langle 0.65, 0.1 \rangle$	$\langle 0.7, 0.5 \rangle$	$\langle 0.9, 0.2 \rangle$	$\langle 0.8, 0.5 \rangle$
X_4	$\langle 0.6, 0.2 \rangle$	$\langle 0.7, 0.1 \rangle$	$\langle 0.7, 0.3 \rangle$	$\langle 0.9, 0.1 \rangle$	$\langle 0.75, 0.2 \rangle$	$\langle 0.9, 0.1 \rangle$	$\langle 0.75, 0.4 \rangle$

First, we ask the decision maker to provide preference on importance of criteria, the interaction between criteria and antagonistic effect between the criteria in the aim of eliciting the parameters associated with the bicapacity within the framework illustrated in Section 5.1. Decision maker provides the following preference information (here we translate the strong inequality into weak inequality with the help of arbitrary variable $\epsilon > 0$):

1. Importance of non-elementary and elementary criteria

- Environmental issue (C_3) is more important than external perception (C_2) i.e., $a_{(3,1)} + a_{(3,2)} \geq a_{(2,1)} + a_{(2,2)} + \epsilon$.
- Management and organization (C_1) is more important than environmental issue (C_3) i.e., $a_{(1,1)} + a_{(1,2)} + a_{(1,3)} \geq a_{(3,1)} + a_{(3,2)} + \epsilon$.

- Reputation and market structure ($c_{(2,1)}$) is more important than certificates ($c_{(2,2)}$) i.e., $a_{(2,1)} \geq a_{(2,2)} + \epsilon$.
- Strategy and organization ($c_{(1,1)}$) is more important than internal management ($c_{(1,2)}$) i.e., $a_{(1,1)} \geq a_{(1,2)} + \epsilon$.
- the crude approximation on the bounds of the elementary criteria $0.1 \leq c_j \leq 0.3$ for all $\mathbf{j} \in EL$

2. Interaction among non-elementary criteria and elementary criteria set

- Strategy and organization ($c_{(1,1)}$) and internal management ($c_{(1,2)}$) are negatively interacting as one elementary criterion exacerbates good effect on the other. Thus to avoid over evaluation it is preferable to reduce the score. We can translate it into a constraint as, $a_{(1,1),(1,2)} \leq -\epsilon$.
- Environmental management ($c_{(3,1)}$) and waste ($c_{(3,2)}$) are positively interacting as good environmental management implies low disposal of waste i.e., they exacerbate bad effect on each other. To balance the synergy between these two elementary criteria, it is necessary to give a bonus. We can translate it into a constraint as, $a_{(3,1),(3,2)} \geq \epsilon$.
- Similarly, there exists an obvious redundancy between reputation and market structure ($c_{(2,1)}$) and certificates ($c_{(2,2)}$). Thus, $a_{(2,1),(2,2)} \leq -\epsilon$.
- Management and organization (C_1) and external perception (C_2) are negatively interacting i.e., specifically, all the elementary criteria descending form C_1 are negatively interacting with all the elementary criteria descending from C_2 . It can be translated into the constraint $\sum_{\mathbf{j}_1 \in I_{C_1}, \mathbf{j}_2 \in I_{C_2}} a_{\mathbf{j}_1, \mathbf{j}_2} \leq 0$. Further decision maker identified that $\{a_{(1,1),(2,1)}, a_{(1,1),(2,2)}, a_{(1,2),(2,1)}, a_{(1,2),(2,2)}, a_{(1,3),(2,1)}, a_{(1,3),(2,2)}\}$ is less or equal to $-\epsilon$.

3. Antagonistic effect between elementary criteria and non-elementary criteria set

- External perception (C_2) has an antagonistic effect over environmental issue (C_3) i.e., specifically, all the elementary criteria descending form C_2 has an antagonistic effect over all the elementary criteria descending from C_3 . This implies, elementary criterion $c_{(2,1)}$ exacerbates antagonistic effect over $\{c_{(3,1)}, c_{(3,2)}\}$ and $c_{(2,2)}$ exacerbates it over $\{c_{(3,1)}, c_{(3,2)}\}$. It can be translated into the constraint, $\sum_{\mathbf{j}_1 \in I_{C_2}, \mathbf{j}_2 \in I_{C_3}} a_{\mathbf{j}_1, \mathbf{j}_2} \leq 0$.

Afterward, we construct the parameter space ε^{DM} by combined the above constraints, which dictated the

decision maker's preference, with the monotonicity and boundary conditions of the bicapacity as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\epsilon^* = \max \quad & \epsilon \\
\text{s.t.} \quad & \left\{ \begin{array}{l}
a_{(3,1)} + a_{(3,2)} \geq a_{(2,1)} + a_{(2,2)} + \epsilon \\
a_{(1,1)} + a_{(1,2)} + a_{(1,3)} \geq a_{(3,1)} + a_{(3,2)} + \epsilon \\
a_{(2,1)} \geq a_{(2,2)} + \epsilon \\
a_{(1,1)} \geq a_{(1,2)} + \epsilon \\
a_{(1,1),(1,2)} \leq -\epsilon \\
a_{(3,1),(3,2)} \geq \epsilon \\
a_{(2,1),(2,2)} \leq -\epsilon \\
a_{\mathbf{j}_1\mathbf{j}_2} \leq -\epsilon, \mathbf{j}_1 \in I_{C_1}, \mathbf{j}_2 \in I_{C_2} \\
\sum_{\mathbf{j}_1 \in I_{C_3}, \mathbf{j}_2 \in I_{C_2}} a_{\mathbf{j}_1\mathbf{j}_2} \leq 0 \\
0.1 \leq c_{\mathbf{j}} \leq 0.3 \text{ for all } \mathbf{j} \in EL \\
a_{\mathbf{j}} + \sum_{\mathbf{j}_1 \in E} a_{\mathbf{j}\mathbf{j}_1} + \sum_{\mathbf{j}_1 \in F} a_{\mathbf{j}\mathbf{j}_1}^+ \geq 0, \forall \mathbf{j} \in EL, \forall (E \cup \{\mathbf{j}\}, F) \in P(\mathcal{C}_{EL}) \\
a_{\mathbf{j}} + \sum_{\mathbf{j}_1 \in F} a_{\mathbf{j}\mathbf{j}_1} + \sum_{\mathbf{j}_1 \in E} a_{\mathbf{j}\mathbf{j}_1}^+ \geq 0, \forall \mathbf{j} \in EL, \forall (E, F \cup \{\mathbf{j}\}) \in P(\mathcal{C}_{EL}) \\
\sum_{\mathbf{j} \in EL} a_{\mathbf{j}} + \sum_{\{\mathbf{j}, \mathbf{j}_1\} \subseteq EL} a_{\mathbf{j}, \mathbf{j}_1} = 1
\end{array} \right. \tag{29}
\end{aligned}$$

The consistency of the preference could be checked by solving the linear programming model (29). For solving the optimization model (29), we have coded the optimization model in *JuMP*¹ (JULia for Mathematical Programming) and called *Clp*² solver to find the optimal solution. We obtained $\epsilon^* = 0.043$, which ensures that the decision maker's preference is consistent and there exist infinitely many compatible sets of parameters.

For the computation of the bipolar preference $I_{\mathbf{j}}^P(X_{\rho}, X_{\beta})$ for any pair of alternatives (X_{ρ}, X_{β}) from pre-order $P \in \mathcal{P}$, we set the parameter associated with q-ROFs as $q = 2.1$, which is the nearest least value of q that satisfies the orthopair fuzzy set condition for all ratings in the Table I. With $q = 2.1$, we compute the closeness indices of the ratings of the alternatives given in Table I and summarized in Table II.

Table II: Closeness index of the ratings

...	$\mathfrak{C}(c_{(1,1)})$	$\mathfrak{C}(c_{(1,2)})$	$\mathfrak{C}(c_{(1,3)})$	$\mathfrak{C}(c_{(2,1)})$	$\mathfrak{C}(c_{(2,2)})$	$\mathfrak{C}(c_{(3,1)})$	$\mathfrak{C}(c_{(3,2)})$
X_1	0.7208	0.5269	0.6469	0.6183	0.6072	0.7208	0.6013
X_2	0.6530	0.5455	0.6358	0.8265	0.6954	0.8038	0.4545
X_3	0.5948	0.5948	0.7262	0.6250	0.5926	0.8295	0.6721
X_4	0.5948	0.6530	0.6358	0.8333	0.6805	0.8333	0.6532

¹<http://www.juliaopt.org/JuMP.jl/v0.13/>

²<https://www.coin-or.org/Clp/>

Before we summarize the results for SMAA methodology, we illustrate the computation of bipolar-QUALIFLEX method under q-ROFs for a sample set of compatible parameters to obtain the best pre-order at the root node C_0 . We report a set of compatible parameters associated with bicapacity that has been sampled from ε^{DM} via Hit-And-Run algorithm in Table III. The rest of the parameters associated with μ are zeros.

Table III: A set of compatible parameters for 2-additive decomposable bicapacity

$a_{(1,1)}$	$a_{(1,2)}$	$a_{(1,3)}$	$a_{(2,1)}$	$a_{(2,2)}$	$a_{(3,1)}$	$a_{(3,2)}$	$a_{(1,1)(1,2)}$	$a_{(1,1)(2,1)}$	$a_{(1,1)(2,2)}$
0.281	0.158	0.146	0.185	0.148	0.133	0.225	-0.019	-0.036	-0.017
$a_{(1,2)(2,1)}$	$a_{(1,2)(2,2)}$	$a_{(1,3)(2,1)}$	$a_{(1,3)(2,2)}$	$a_{(2,1)(2,2)}$	$a_{(3,1)(3,2)}$	$a_{(3,1) (2,1)}$	$a_{(3,2) (2,1)}$	$a_{(3,1) (2,2)}$	$a_{(3,2) (2,2)}$
-0.015	-0.035	-0.017	-0.015	-0.031	0.01	-0.036	-0.04	-0.009	-0.015

As $|\mathbb{X}| = 4$, there are 24 pre-orders in \mathcal{P} . Let $P_1 = (X_4, X_3, X_2, X_1)$ be a pre-order from \mathcal{P} . For the different pairs of alternatives $(X_\rho, X_\beta) \in P_1$, we compute the bipolar preferences against each elementary criteria c_j $j \in EL$ by using Eq. (17) as follows: By utilizing Eqs. (18)-(19) with the 2-additive decomposition of

Table IV: concordance/discordance index for different pairs of alternatives against elementary criteria

...	$c_{(1,1)}$	$c_{(1,2)}$	$c_{(1,3)}$	$c_{(2,1)}$	$c_{(2,2)}$	$c_{(3,1)}$	$c_{(3,2)}$
$I_j^{P_1}(X_4, X_3)$	0	0.0582	-0.0904	0.2083	0.0880	0.0037	-0.0189
$I_j^{P_1}(X_4, X_2)$	-0.0582	0.1075	0	0.0068	-0.0148	0.0295	0.1987
$I_j^{P_1}(X_4, X_1)$	-0.1260	0.1261	-0.0112	0.2150	0.0733	0.1125	0.0519
$I_j^{P_1}(X_3, X_2)$	-0.0582	0.0494	0.0904	-0.2015	-0.1028	0.0258	0.2176
$I_j^{P_1}(X_3, X_1)$	-0.1260	0.0679	0.0792	0.0066	-0.0146	0.1087	0.0708
$I_j^{P_1}(X_2, X_1)$	-0.0678	0.0186	-0.0112	0.2082	0.0882	0.0830	-0.1467

the bicapacity μ , described in Table III, we compute overall concordance/discordance index for each pairs of alternatives $(X_\rho, X_\beta) \in P_1$ from Table IV as follows:

Table V: concordance/discordance index for different pairs of alternatives against elementary criteria

$I^{P_1}(X_4, X_3)$	$I^{P_1}(X_4, X_2)$	$I^{P_1}(X_4, X_1)$	$I^{P_1}(X_3, X_2)$	$I^{P_1}(X_3, X_1)$	$I^{P_1}(X_2, X_1)$
0.0325	0.0491	0.0477	0.0175	0.0178	0.0045

By utilizing the Eq. (21), we obtain the overall concordance/discordance evidence for the pre-order P_1 as follows: $I^{P_1} = 0.1692$. In a similar manner, we compute the overall concordance/discordance evidence for the other pre-orders from \mathcal{P} and summarize the results in Table VI. From Table VI, it is clear that P_1 is the best possible pre-order of the alternatives. Hence the ranking order of the alternatives at the root node C_0 is as follows: $X_4 \succ X_3 \succ X_2 \succ X_1$.

Next, we illustrate the computation for finding the best pre-order at the non-elementary node C_1 with the same set of parameters for the bicapacity μ , given in Table III. Let us consider the evaluation of the overall concordance/discordance of the pair of alternative $(X_3, X_2) \in P_1$. For $(X_3, X_2) \in P_1$ the bi-polar preference vector can be obtained from Table IV by using Eq. (IV) as follows: $[I_j^P(X_3, X_2) : j \in EL]_1 = [-0.0582, 0.0494, 0.0904, 0, 0, 0, 0]$.

Table VI: Overall concordance/discordance index for all possible pre-orders

P	I^P	P	I^P	P	I^P
$P_1 = (X_4, X_3, X_2, X_1)$	0.1692	$P_2 = (X_4, X_3, X_1, X_2)$	0.1601	$P_3 = (X_4, X_2, X_3, X_1)$	0.1342
$P_4 = (X_4, X_3, X_1, X_3)$	0.0986	$P_5 = (X_4, X_1, X_3, X_2)$	0.1245	$P_6 = (X_4, X_1, X_2, X_3)$	0.0895
$P_7 = (X_3, X_4, X_2, X_1)$	0.1041	$P_8 = (X_3, X_4, X_1, X_2)$	0.0950	$P_9 = (X_3, X_2, X_4, X_1)$	0.0058
$P_{10} = (X_3, X_2, X_1, X_4)$	-0.0895	$P_{11} = (X_3, X_1, X_4, X_2)$	-0.0003	$P_{12} = (X_3, X_1, X_2, X_4)$	-0.0986
$P_{13} = (X_2, X_4, X_3, X_1)$	0.0359	$P_{14} = (X_2, X_4, X_1, X_3)$	0.0003	$P_{15} = (X_2, X_3, X_4, X_1)$	-0.0292
$P_{16} = (X_2, X_3, X_1, X_4)$	-0.1245	$P_{17} = (X_2, X_1, X_4, X_3)$	-0.0950	$P_{18} = (X_2, X_1, X_3, X_4)$	-0.1601
$P_{19} = (X_1, X_4, X_3, X_2)$	0.0292	$P_{20} = (X_1, X_4, X_2, X_3)$	-0.0058	$P_{21} = (X_1, X_3, X_4, X_2)$	-0.0359
$P_{22} = (X_1, X_3, X_2, X_4)$	-0.1342	$P_{23} = (X_1, X_2, X_4, X_3)$	-0.1041	$P_{24} = (X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4)$	-0.1692

With the help of Eq. (22), we find the overall concordance evidence as follows:

$$I_1^{P+}(X_3, X_2) = C_{\mu_1^h}^{B+}([I_j^P(X_3, X_2) : \mathbf{j} \in EL]_1) = \frac{C_{\mu}^{B+}([-0.0582, 0.0494, 0.0904, 0, 0, 0, 0])}{\mu^+(\{c_j : \mathbf{j} \in I_{C_1}\}, \emptyset)}$$

By Eq. (19) with the 2-additive decomposable bicapacity parameters of μ , given in Table III, we have

$$\begin{aligned} C_{\mu}^{B+}([-0.0582, 0.0494, 0.0904, 0, 0, 0, 0]) &= 0.0494a_{(1,2)} + 0.0904a_{(1,3)} + a_{(1,2),(1,3)} \min\{0.0494, 0.0904\} + \\ & a_{(1,2)|(1,1)} \min\{0.0494, 0.0582\} + a_{(1,2)|(1,1)} \min\{0.0904, 0.0582\} \\ &= 0.0494 \times 0.158 + 0.0904 \times 0.146 = 0.021. \end{aligned}$$

By utilizing the 2-additive decomposition of the bicapacity with symmetry condition and considering the bicapacity parameters in Table III, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mu^+(\{c_j : \mathbf{j} \in I_{C_1}\}, \emptyset) &= \mu(\{c_{(1,1)}, c_{(1,2)}, c_{1,3}\}, \emptyset) \\ &= a_{(1,1)} + a_{(1,2)} + a_{1,3} + a_{(1,1)(1,2)} + a_{(1,1)(1,3)} + a_{(1,2)(1,3)} \\ &= 0.281 + 0.158 + 0.146 - 0.019 = 0.5660 \end{aligned}$$

Consequently $\frac{C_{\mu}^{B+}([-0.0582, 0.0494, 0.0904, 0, 0, 0, 0])}{\mu^+(\{c_j : \mathbf{j} \in I_{C_1}\}, \emptyset)} = \frac{0.021}{0.5660} = 0.0371$. Similarly, we obtain $I_1^{P-}(X_3, X_2) = 0.0324$. Therefore, $I_1^P(X_3, X_2) = I_1^{P+}(X_3, X_2) - I_1^{P-}(X_3, X_2) = 0.0047$. In a similar manner, we can obtain overall concordance/discordance for the other pairs of alternatives in P_1 and subsequently, obtain the overall concordance/discordance index for P_1 and report it Table VII along with other pre-orders overall concordance/discordance indices. From Table , it is clear that $P_{21} = (X_1, X_3, X_4, X_2)$ is the best possible pre-order of the alternatives with respect to the aspect M&O. Thus, the ranking order with respect to the aspect M&O becomes: $X_1 \succ X_3 \succ X_4 \succ X_2$. Analogously, one can find the best possible pre-orders $X_2 \succ X_4 \succ X_1 \succ X_3$ and $X_3 \succ X_4 \succ X_1 \succ X_2$ for the non-elementary nodes C_2 and C_3 , respectively. This process of finding the best pre-orders at all non-elementary nodes is repeated within the framework of SMAA to find robust recommendation considering all the compatible set of parameters and that has been described in the following.

Now, we can employ the SMAA methodology to find a robust recommendation for the supplier selection

Table VII: Overall concordance/discordance index for all possible pre-orders at C_1

P	I_1^P	P	I_1^P	P	I_1^P
$P_1 = (X_4, X_3, X_2, X_1)$	-0.0824	$P_2 = (X_4, X_3, X_1, X_2)$	-0.0198	$P_3 = (X_4, X_2, X_3, X_1)$	-0.0989
$P_4 = (X_4, X_3, X_1, X_3)$	-0.0528	$P_5 = (X_4, X_1, X_3, X_2)$	0.0264	$P_6 = (X_4, X_1, X_2, X_3)$	0.0099
$P_7 = (X_3, X_4, X_2, X_1)$	-0.0681	$P_8 = (X_3, X_4, X_1, X_2)$	-0.0055	$P_9 = (X_3, X_2, X_4, X_1)$	-0.0704
$P_{10} = (X_3, X_2, X_1, X_4)$	-0.0099	$P_{11} = (X_3, X_1, X_4, X_2)$	0.0550	$P_{12} = (X_3, X_1, X_2, X_4)$	0.0528
$P_{13} = (X_2, X_4, X_3, X_1)$	-0.1012	$P_{14} = (X_2, X_4, X_1, X_3)$	-0.0550	$P_{15} = (X_2, X_3, X_4, X_1)$	-0.0869
$P_{16} = (X_2, X_3, X_1, X_4)$	-0.0264	$P_{17} = (X_2, X_1, X_4, X_3)$	0.0055	$P_{18} = (X_2, X_1, X_3, X_4)$	0.0198
$P_{19} = (X_1, X_4, X_3, X_2)$	0.0869	$P_{20} = (X_1, X_4, X_2, X_3)$	0.0704	$P_{21} = (X_1, X_3, X_4, X_2)$	0.1012
$P_{22} = (X_1, X_3, X_2, X_4)$	0.0989	$P_{23} = (X_1, X_2, X_4, X_3)$	0.0681	$P_{24} = (X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4)$	0.0824

problem. In particular, we have employed Hit-and-Run algorithm to sample 10,000 compatible set of parameters from the parameters space ε^{DM} and for each compatible set of parameters we found the best pre-order of the alternatives at the comprehensive level (root node C_0 of the hierarchy) and intermediate levels (non-elementary criteria C_1 , C_2 and C_3). After termination of all iterations, we have computed the rank acceptability indices $b_r^k(X_i)$ for each alternative X_i regarding k -th ranking position at node C_r , where $i, k = 1, 2, 3, 4$ and $r = \mathbf{0}, \mathbf{1}, \mathbf{2}, \mathbf{3}$. Further, we have obtained pairwise winning indices $p_r(X_{i_1}, X_{i_2})$ for each of the pair of alternatives (X_{i_1}, X_{i_2}) , where $i_1, i_2 = 1, 2, 3, 4$ at nodes C_r ($r = \mathbf{0}, \mathbf{1}, \mathbf{2}, \mathbf{3}$) of the hierarchy. The results are summarized in Tables VIII and IX to obtain the final comprehensive ordering relation with respect to the whole set of criteria and partial ordering relations with respect to non-elementary criterion at a given level of the hierarchy. In the next section, we analyze the ranking results obtained by the proposed SMAA based MCHP-bipolar QUALIFLEX under q-ROFS.

5.1. Ranking results at comprehensive level

Now, analyzing Table VIII(a) it is clear that the alternative X_4 is the most preferable for the first rank with the rank acceptability index 99.98% at the comprehensive level. Although alternative X_3 is also potentially optimal and could fill the first position in the final rank as it has rank acceptability greater than 0. Further, to see how the alternative X_3 performs with respect to the rest of the alternatives, we look into the pairwise winning index Table VIII(b) and found that X_4 is preferred than other with a frequency of at least 0.9998. Therefore it is confirmed that X_4 is considered as the best supplier among all four. Apart from that, X_3 can be considered as the second-best supplier as it is preferred to other suppliers except for X_4 with a percentage of at least 0.8679. But the X_2 has the potential to occupy the second-ranking position with the rank acceptability 13.21%. The alternative X_2 has high-rank acceptability for occupying the third-ranking position in comparison to X_1 and X_3 . On the contrary from both the Table, X_1 accrues the last ranking position and all the other suppliers are more preferable than it in most of the time. Thus, finally from Table VIII(a) and (b), we can obtain the comprehensive ordering relation with respect to the whole set of criteria as $X_4 \succ X_3 \succ X_2 \succ X_1$.

5.2. Ranking results at intermediate level

Analogously, one can analyze the ordering relations among the alternatives with respect to individual aspects M&O, EP, and EVS of the supplier evaluation. Since M&O is the most important aspect according to the decision

Table VIII: Comprehensive results obtained by SMAA-QUALIFLEX methodology under q-rung fuzzy set

(a) RAI's of the alternatives at comprehensive level					(b) PWI's of the alternatives at comprehensive level				
	$b_0^1(X_i)$	$b_0^2(X_i)$	$b_0^3(X_i)$	$b_0^4(X_i)$		X_1	X_2	X_3	X_4
X_1	0	0	5.23	94.77	X_1	0	0.0523	0	0
X_2	0	13.21	81.56	5.23	X_2	0.9477	0	0.1321	0
X_3	0.02	86.78	13.2	0	X_3	1	0.8679	0	0.0002
X_4	99.98	0.02	0	0	X_4	1	1	0.9998	0

maker's preference, we focus on analyzing the performance of the alternatives under this aspect. From Table IX(c) and (d), it is quite difficult to elicit the complete ordering relation of the alternatives as the robustness information in terms of RAI and PWI is not enough to discern a certain order between alternatives with sufficient conformity. The PWI demonstrate that the alternative X_1 is certainly preferred to X_2 and X_4 while X_3 is preferred to X_2 and X_4 in most of the cases. But the conformity for the preference X_1 over X_3 is not very high enough to discern it with certainty. At the same time, X_2 deems as the worst supplier as all the other suppliers are more preferable than it with sufficient robustness information. In sum, the most possible ranking orderings of the alternatives against M&O aspect is $X_1 \succ X_3 \succ X_4 \succ X_2$ while there is some evidence to support the ordering relation $X_3 \succ X_1 \succ X_4 \succ X_2$. We made a similar investigation regarding the aspects EP and EVS and report the ranking orders of the alternatives in Table X.

Table IX: Partial results obtained by SMAA-QUALIFLEX methodology under q-rung fuzzy set

(c) RAI's of the alternatives w.r.t management					(d) PWI's of the alternatives w.r.t management				
	$b_1^1(X_i)$	$b_1^2(X_i)$	$b_1^3(X_i)$	$b_1^4(X_i)$		X_1	X_2	X_3	X_4
X_1	64.49	35.51	0	0	X_1	0	1	0.6449	1
X_2	0	1.65	19.13	79.22	X_2	0	0	0.0167	0.2076
X_3	35.51	56.68	7.79	0.02	X_3	0.3551	0.9833	0	0.9384
X_4	0	6.16	73.08	20.76	X_4	0	0.7924	0.0616	0

(e) RAI's of the alternatives w.r.t external perception					(f) PWI's of the alternatives w.r.t external perception				
	$b_2^1(X_i)$	$b_2^2(X_i)$	$b_2^3(X_i)$	$b_2^4(X_i)$		X_1	X_2	X_3	X_4
X_1	0	0	98.36	1.64	X_1	0	0	0.9836	0
X_2	98.3	1.7	0	0	X_2	1	0	1	0.9830
X_3	0	0	1.64	98.36	X_3	0.0164	0	0	0
X_4	1.7	98.3	0	0	X_4	1	0.017	1	0

(g) RAI's of the alternatives w.r.t environmental issue					(h) PWI's of the alternatives w.r.t environmental issue				
	$b_3^1(X_i)$	$b_3^2(X_i)$	$b_3^3(X_i)$	$b_3^4(X_i)$		X_1	X_2	X_3	X_4
X_1	0	0	82.65	17.35	X_1	0	0.8265	0	0
X_2	0	0	17.35	82.65	X_2	0.1735	0	0	0
X_3	100	0	0	0	X_3	1	1	0	1
X_4	0	100	0	0	X_4	1	1	0	0

As a matter of fact, analyzing the entire Table IX under the aspects M&O, EP, and EVS, one can observe that X_1 , X_2 and X_3 are respectively the best among all four suppliers with highest first rank acceptability indices. Thus it is interesting to have the supplier X_1 as the best one concerning the aspect M&O while it ensures the last position in respect to comprehensive outcome. Also we observe that, supplier X_3 is preferred to supplier X_2

with respect to entire criteria set but the reverse has happened when we consider only the aspect EP. Therefore, in order to investigate the significance of a particular aspect over the rank ordering of alternatives assessment of partial results are very beneficial. The optimal ranking obtained by MCHP-QUALIFLEX-SMAA for each criteria/ sub-criterion of the hierarchy is summarized in Table X.

Table X: Ranking of suppliers at all the level of the hierarchical structure of criteria set

Ranking	Comprehensive	Management and organization	External perception	Environmental issues
1	X_4	X_1	X_2	X_3
2	X_3	X_3	X_4	X_4
3	X_2	X_4	X_1	X_1
4	X_1	X_2	X_3	X_2

6. Conclusions

In this present study we have proposed a methodology to handle the following intents simultaneously: (i) estimation of criteria set under q-ROF environment, (ii) handling set of criteria structured into hierarchical fashion, (iii) dealing interaction among the elementary nodes of the criteria set, and (iv) consideration of variety of preference parameters assigned in accordance with the statistics provided by the decision makers.

To tackle all previous issues conjointly, first we have discussed the novel concept of q-ROFS and reviewed the basic operations along with the distance measure. Subsequently, we have suggested a new concept of closeness index for q-ROFS and introduced a total ordering based on the defined closeness index. Secondly, we have developed a closeness index based q-rung fuzzy QUALIFLEX methodology addressing hierarchical structure of criteria set where decision makers are capable of estimating results not only at the comprehensive level but also for a particular sub-criterion at some intermediate level of the hierarchy. Thirdly, in the aforementioned extended QUALIFLEX method we have aggregated the elementary nodes of the hierarchical structure of criteria set with the help of bipolar Choquet integral in the intention of capturing possible interactions among them. Fourthly, we have applied SMAA to take into account the variety of parameters set concerning the relative importance and interaction of different criteria in order to verify the stability of the result. Finally, we have provided a numerical example where our proposed methodology has been applied in addition to some analysis to highlight the advantages of our proposed combined SMAA-QUALIFLEX methodology.

Acknowledgement

The first and third authors are supported by the grant no. ECR/2016/001908 from SERB, New Delhi

References

- [1] Zadeh LA. Fuzzy sets. Inform Control. 1965;8(3):338–353.

- [2] Pedrycz W, Ekel P. Fuzzy Multicriteria Decision Making: Models, Methods and Applications. Wiley; 2011.
- [3] Atanassov, KT. Intuitionistic fuzzy sets. *Fuzzy Sets Syst* 1986;20(1):87–96.
- [4] Yager RR. Pythagorean membership grades in multicriteria decision making. *IEEE Trans Fuzzy Syst.* 2014;22(4):958–965.
- [5] Yager RR. Generalized orthopair fuzzy sets. *IEEE Trans Fuzzy Syst.* 2017;25(5):1222–1230.
- [6] Liu P, Wang P. Some q-rung orthopair fuzzy aggregation operators and their applications to multiple-attribute decision making. *Int J Intell Syst.* 2018;33(2):259–280.
- [7] Liu P, Liu J. Some q-rung orthopair fuzzy Bonferroni mean operators and their application to multi-attribute group decision making. *Int J Intell Syst* 2018;33(2):315–347.
- [8] Liu Z, Wang S, Liu, P. Multiple attribute group decision making based on q-rung orthopair fuzzy Heronian mean operators. *Int J Intell Syst.* 2018;33(12):2341–2363.
- [9] Peng X, Dai J, Garg, H. Exponential operation and aggregation operator for q-rung orthopair fuzzy set and their decision-making method with a new score function. *Int J Intell Syst.* 2018;33:2255–2282.
- [10] Liu D, Chen X, Peng D. Some cosine similarity measures and distance measures between q-rung orthopair fuzzy sets. *Int J Intell Syst.* 2019;34(7):1572–1587.
- [11] Yang W, Pang Y. New q-rung orthopair fuzzy partitioned Bonferroni mean operators and their application in multiple attribute decision making. *Int J Intell Syst.* 2019;34(3):439–476.
- [12] Shu X, Ai Z, Xu Z, Ye J. Integrations of q-rung orthopair fuzzy continuous information. *IEEE Trans Fuzzy Syst.* 2019; doi.10.1109/TFUZZ.2019.2893205.
- [13] Jan N, Mahmood T, Zedam L, Ullah K, Alcantud JCR, Davvaz B. Analysis of social networks, communication networks and shortest path problems in the environment of interval-valued q-rung orthopair fuzzy graphs. *Int J Fuzzy Syst.* 2019;21(6):1687–1708.
- [14] Paelinck, JH. Qualitative multiple criteria analysis, environmental protection and multi-regional development. *Pap Reg Sci.* 1976;36(1):59–74.
- [15] Paelinck J. Qualitative multicriteria analysis: an application to airport location. *Environ Plann A.* 1977;9(8):883–895.
- [16] Paelinck, JH. QUALIFLEX: a flexible multiple-criteria method. *Econ Lett.* 1978;1(3):193–197.
- [17] Chen TY, Chang CH, Lu, JR.. The extended QUALIFLEX method for multiple criteria decision analysis based on interval type-2 fuzzy sets and applications to medical decision making. *Eur J Oper Res.* 2013;226(3):615–625.

- [18] Wang JC, Tsao CY, Chen, TY. A likelihood-based QUALIFLEX method with interval type-2 fuzzy sets for multiple criteria decision analysis. *Soft Comput.* 2015;19(8):2225–2243.
- [19] Zhang X. Multicriteria pythagorean fuzzy decision analysis: A hierarchical QUALIFLEX approach with the closeness index-based ranking methods. *Inform Sci.* 2016;330:104–124.
- [20] Li J, Wang J. An extended QUALIFLEX method under probability hesitant fuzzy environment for selecting green suppliers. *Int J Fuzzy Syst.* 2017;19(6):1866–1879.
- [21] Peng J, Wang J, Yang WE. A multi-valued neutrosophic qualitative flexible approach based on likelihood for multi-criteria decision-making problems. *Int J of Syst Sci.* 2017;48:425–435.
- [22] Zhang Z. Multi-criteria decision-making using interval-valued hesitant fuzzy QUALIFLEX methods based on a likelihood-based comparison approach. *Neural Comput Appl.* 2017;28(7):1835–1854.
- [23] Zhang X, Xu Z. Hesitant fuzzy QUALIFLEX approach with a signed distance-based comparison method for multiple criteria decision analysis. *Expert Syst Appl.* 2015;42:873–884.
- [24] Chen TY. Data construction process and QUALIFLEX based method for multiple-criteria group decision making with interval valued intuitionistic fuzzy sets. *Int J Inform Tech Decis Mak.* 2013;12:425–467.
- [25] Tian Z, Wang J, Wang J, Zhang, H. A likelihood-based qualitative flexible approach with hesitant fuzzy linguistic information. *Cogn Comput.* 2016;8(4):670–683.
- [26] Chen, TY. Interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy QUALIFLEX method with a likelihood-based comparison approach for multiple criteria decision analysis. *Inform Sci.* 2014;261:149–169.
- [27] Keeney RL, Raiffa H. *Decisions with multiple objectives : preferences and value trade-offs.* Cambridge University Press; 1993.
- [28] Corrente S, Greco S, Słowiński R. Multiple criteria hierarchy process in robust ordinal regression. *Decis Support Syst.* 2012;53(3):660–674.
- [29] Corrente S, Greco S, Słowiński R. Multiple criteria hierarchy process with ELECTRE and promethee. *OMEGA-Int J Manage Sci.* 2013;41(5):820–846.
- [30] Corrente S, Figueira JR, Greco S, Słowiński R. A robust ranking method extending ELECTRE iii to hierarchy of interacting criteria, imprecise weights and stochastic analysis. *OMEGA-Int J Manage Sci.* 2017;73:1–17.
- [31] Choquet G. Theory of capacities. *Annales de l’Institut Fourier.* 1954;5:131–295.
- [32] Marichal JL. An axiomatic approach of the discrete Choquet integral as a tool to aggregate interacting criteria. *IEEE Trans Fuzzy Syst.* 2000;8(6):800–807.

- [33] Grabisch M, Labreuche C. A decade of application of the Choquet and Sugeno integrals in multi-criteria decision aid. *Ann Oper Res.* 2010;175:247–286.
- [34] Corrente S, Figueira JR, Greco S. Dealing with interaction between bipolar multiple criteria preferences in promethee methods. *Ann Oper Res.* 2014;217:137–164.
- [35] Arcidiacono SG, Corrente S, Greco S. GAIA-SMAA-PROMETHEE for a hierarchy of interacting criteria. *Eur J Oper Res.* 2018;270:606–624.
- [36] Figueira JR, Greco S, Roy B. ELETRE methods with interaction between criteria: An extension of the concordance index. *Eur J Oper Res.* 2009;199:478–495.
- [37] Greco S, Matarazzo B, Słowiński, R. In: *Proc of EUROFUSE workshop on information systems*, 2002:191–196.
- [38] Greco S, Figueira JR. Dealing with interaction between bi-polar multiple criteria preferences in outranking methods. *Research Report 11–2003, INESC - Coimbra, Portugal* 2003.
- [39] Grabisch M, Labreuche C. Bi-capacities-II: the Choquet integral. *Fuzzy Sets Syst.* 2005;151:237–259.
- [40] Grabisch M, Labreuche C. Bi-capacities-I: definition, mobius transform and interaction. *Fuzzy Sets Syst.* 2005;151:211–236.
- [41] Grabisch M, Kojadinovic I, Meyer P. A review of methods for capacity identification in Choquet integral based multi-attribute utility theory: Applications of the Kappalab R package. *Eur J Oper Res.* 2008;186:766–785.
- [42] Angilella S, Corrente S, Greco S. Stochastic multiobjective acceptability analysis for the choquet integral preference model and the scale construction problem. *Eur J Oper Res.* 2015;240:172–182.
- [43] Rowley HV, Geschke A, Lenzen M. A practical approach for estimating weights of interacting criteria from profile sets. *Fuzzy Sets Syst* 2015;272:70–88.
- [44] Angilella S, Catalfo P, Corrente S, Giarlotta A, Greco S, Rizzo, M. Robust sustainable development assessment with composite indices aggregating interacting dimensions: The hierarchical-SMAA-Choquet integral approach. *Knowl-Based Syst.* 2018;158:136–153.
- [45] Lahdelma R, Hokkanen J, Salminen P. SMAA - stochastic multiobjective acceptability analysis. *Eur J Oper Res.* 1998;106:137–143.
- [46] Tervonen T, Lahdelma R. Implementing stochastic multicriteria acceptability analysis. *Eur J Oper Res.* 2007;178:500–513.
- [47] Corrente S, Figueira JR, Greco S. The SMAA-PROMETHEE method. *Eur J Oper Res.* 2014;239:514–522.

- [48] Greco S, Rindone F. Bipolar fuzzy integrals. *Fuzzy Sets and Syst.* 2013;220:21–33.
- [49] Zhang X, Xu Z. Extension of TOPSIS to multiple criteria decision making with pythagorean fuzzy sets. *Int J Intell Syst.* 2014;29(12):1061–1078.
- [50] Hwang CL, Yoon K. Multiple attribute decision making : methods and applications, a State of the Art survey. Springer Berlin Heidelberg; 1981.
- [51] Jacquet-Lagrece, E., Siskos, Y.. Preference disaggregation: 20 years of MCDA experience. *Eur J Oper Res.* 2001;130(2):233–245.
- [52] Park KS, Kim SH, Yoon WC. Establishing strict dominance between alternatives with special type of incomplete information. *Eur J Oper Res.* 1997;96(2):398–406.
- [53] Mousseau V, Figueira JR, Dias L, Gomes da Silva C, Clmaco J. Resolving inconsistencies among constraints on the parameters of an mcda model. *Eur J Oper Res.* 2003;147:72–93.
- [54] Lahdelma R, Salminen P. SMAA-2: Stochastic Multicriteria Acceptability Analysis for Group Decision Making. *Oper Res.* 2001;49:444–454.
- [55] Pelissari R, Oliveira M, Amor SB, Kandakoglu A, Helleno A. SMAA methods and their applications: a literature review and future research directions. *Anna Oper Res.* 2019;doi.org/10.1007/s10479-019-03151-z.